

The Facilitator's Toolkit. A Manual for Digital Facilitators of Adults 55+

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Digital Facilitator for Adults 55+

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DIFA

The Facilitator's Toolkit. A Manual for Digital Facilitators of Adults 55+

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Abstract	<p>Being a digital facilitator requires having a set of specific skills, knowledge, abilities and behaviours enabling digital educators to operate effectively in online and offline adult education. According to the DigCompEdu, there are six main areas relevant for digital facilitators, namely: Professional Engagement, Digital Resources, Teaching and Learning, Assessment, Empowering Learners and Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence (Redecker 2017).</p> <p>To advance the lifelong learning and integration of adults 55+ in society and to ease their transition from employment to retirement, the entire educational construct needs to be adapted compared to other age groups. This educational construct includes, for example, answering fundamental questions such as: what topics are being addressed, where the training activities take place, when or for what period and, most importantly, how the training and non-formal education is being designed and delivered. The answer to these questions rests with the adult education providers but, ultimately, with their trainers and facilitators who work directly with adults 55+.</p> <p>The Covid-19 pandemic restricted to a great extent many facilitators and trainers from organising face-to-face activities. Therefore, during the</p>

	<p>pandemic period, they had to deliver their non-formal education activities in hybrid or online modes. This implied using digital tools which required them to learn how to design and deliver activities using digital tools but also to train adults 55+ on using those digital tools. Overall, the profile of trainers changed from facilitators to digital facilitators.</p> <p>In this manual, the project researchers and adult educators developed a research methodology, implemented it through primary research (survey) and desk research (finding and analysing good practices), fed the research into a competence map, developed an online self-assessment tool for digital facilitators of adults 55+ and curated a toolbox which assists digital facilitators of adults 55+ in bridging their competence gaps.</p> <p>Conclusions, recommendations and transferability outlook are included to invite the recipients of this document to proper usage of the same.</p>
<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Adult education, research methodology, desk research, good practices, research survey, instructional design, digital transformation, digital tools, digital resources, digital competence, non-formal education, competence framework, DigComp, DigCompEdu, competence map, self-assessment, adult learners, adults 55+, elderly, adult educators, digital facilitators</p>

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Summary

Being a digital facilitator requires having a set of specific skills, knowledge, abilities and behaviours enabling digital educators to operate effectively in online and offline adult education. According to the DigCompEdu, there are six main areas relevant for digital facilitators, namely: Professional Engagement, Digital Resources, Teaching and Learning, Assessment, Empowering Learners and Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence (Redecker 2017).

In this manual, the project researchers and adult educators developed a research methodology, implemented it through primary research (survey) and desk research (finding and analysing good practices), fed the research into a competence map, developed an online self-assessment tool for digital facilitators of adults 55+ and curated a toolbox which assists digital facilitators of adults 55+ in bridging their competence gaps.

This manual is part of the Erasmus+ project "[DIFA - Digital Facilitator for Adults 55+](#)", implemented by a consortium of four partners from Romania, Spain and Turkey. The project aims to develop, test and implement an innovative digital education ecosystem with supportive tools to let educators create, share and adapt attractive learning activities for the development of digital skills of adults 55+.

Chapter 1 represents the research methodology developed and implemented by the research consortium, in line with the DIFA55+ project objectives, qualitative and quantitative performance indicators as well as the impact and sustainability ambitions of the project.

Following up on the methodology, in **Chapter 2** researchers from Formative Footprint (Spain), TEAM4Excellence (Romania), Voluntariat Pentru Viata (Romania) and Saricam Halk Egitimi Merkezi (Turkey) contributed to the development, data collection and analysis of a survey as a primary research method. The survey aimed to investigate adult learners' readiness for digital media in their surroundings.

In **Chapter 3**, partners' researchers approached the research of digital pedagogical practices through instructional design models (ADDIE, 5E) and yet defined the national and European digital educational environment where the 55+ adult educators operate, as a useful need analysis assessment.

As the current research showed, digital facilitators of adults 55+ need a specific competence map and tools to assess their current competence across the competence map. **Chapter 4** focuses on the competence map and the [online self-assessment instrument](#) designed by the research team to identify competence gaps in the six areas set out by the DigCompEdu framework.

Chapter 5 represents a collection of tools which assist digital facilitators of adults 55+ in bridging the competence gaps. It sought to expand the research into the tools that may assist digital facilitators of adults 55+ in rounding their knowledge, attitudes and skills in the six areas that compose the competence map. It is thought that these will further assist field educators in designing and delivering digital courses. For clarity, in the scope of the current manual, digital courses include face-to-face, hybrid and online courses that employ digital technology to support the creation and delivery of non-formal courses for adults 55+. The toolbox assembled by the research team is structured to mirror the competence map.

Finally, the manual formulates conclusions and recommendations, as well as provides a usability and transferability potential outlook of the manual to other target groups and educational contexts.

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Introduction

The pandemic's impact has spiralled the EU into a deep recession and increased the digital divide. The digital exclusion during the pandemic affected adults aged 55+ in several ways. Many of them were not able to readily access health advice, medical appointments, or support services for housing or social care. The pandemic also had an adverse impact on people seeking work, as those who are less digitally skilled (especially adults 55+) or do not have internet access may struggle to search for and apply for jobs online and may not be able to access online employment support services.

Digital skills are important for managing mental health during social distancing, not just for communicating with friends and family, but also because many social and welfare activities are now being offered online. There are also concerns that those without digital skills may find it harder to access and manage their finances, as banks and retailers have increasingly encouraged their customers to use online services.

The European Commission recommended accelerating the much-needed digital transition and gave priority to investments in digital learning infrastructure and technology. While education providers focused on making the education offer available online, the quality of online pedagogy was not the first concern. Therefore, there is an urgency to increase the quality of the instructional design, improve the quality and ensure that learners reach the desired learning outcomes (European Commission, 2020).

Education plays a decisive role and according to the Active Ageing Report (UNECE, 2019) the involvement in the education of adults (55-74), varies among the 28 EU countries from 0.2% in Romania and 3.1% in Spain to 19.3% in Denmark. The very fast digitalization forced educators to make education offer available online and the quality of online pedagogy was not the first concern. This does not only require providers and staff to have digital competences but also – and even more so – requires strong tutoring and assessment skills and the ability to be flexible and adaptable to changing circumstances.

In this context, the DIFA project aims to develop, test and implement an innovative digital education ecosystem with supportive tools to let educators create, share and adapt attractive learning activities for the development of digital skills of adults. In order to do this, educators and other adult education staff need to develop their digital skills and use appropriate teaching methods and tools adapted to digital education. At the same time, adult education organisations need to improve their capacities to address the real needs of adults 55+.

The current manual addresses the above by equipping Digital Facilitators not only with digital pedagogy skills but also with a related set of tools and instruments adaptable and re-useable using the instructional design models. A competence map and a self-assessment tool for digital facilitators were considered necessary to give an understanding of the digital facilitator's role to engage adults 55+ and help them become digitally-competent citizens. This manual is expected to expand the competences of educators and other adult education staff making them digitally competent and confident teachers and education and training staff.

The DIFA project is an opportunity to bring together a multi-disciplinary, complementary partnership consisting of four partners from Romania (an NGO specialized in digital education and an NGO providing support to elderly centres), Spain (an institute specialized in design training processes), and Turkey (a regional umbrella organization for adult education centres).

Chapter 1. Research methodology

1.1 Aim of the research

In the framework of the DIFA55+ project objectives, the current research follows certain qualitative and quantitative performance indicators, with great relevance for the impact and sustainability of the project on the three distinct target groups. As such, the project enhances the capacity of 40 EDUCATORS and 20 adult ORGANIZATIONS in their support for 150 ADULTS 55+ to be active technology users. That is being done by improving the digital facilitator competencies of educators and other adult education staff via using a toolbox of instruments for creating engaging and active learning and digital pedagogies adapted to proficiency levels.

Research has been conducted in all the partner countries (Romania, Spain, Turkey) in order to assess the instruments and tools for digital learning environments and adapt them to adult 55+ education.

1.2 Research method

The Digital Facilitator Toolkit project result is focused on the analysis of the most successful tools and instruments - from the perspective of instructional design models ADDIE and 5E - and improvements, as resulting from adults' and educators' input.

The ADDIE model is a process implemented for instructional designing and training developing. It contemplates 5 stages:

- ANALYSIS. In the analysis phase, the instructional challenge is made clear, the goals and objectives are set, the learning environment is determined, and the learner's prior knowledge and skills are noted.
- DESIGN. Learning objectives, assessment tools, activities, content, subject matter analysis, lesson preparation, and media choice are all covered in the design process. The design process ought to be methodical and precise.
- DEVELOPMENT. The content assets that were produced during the design phase are created and assembled by the developers during the development phase.
- IMPLEMENTATION. A process for educating the facilitators and the learners is created during the implementation phase. The course curriculum, learning objectives, delivery strategy, and testing procedures should all be covered in the facilitators' training.
- EVALUATION. The evaluation phase is divided into formative and summative components. Each level of the ADDIE process includes formative evaluation. Summative assessment comprises of exams created for criterion-related referenced items that are domain-specific and offer chances for user response.

The 5E model is a reference model to build up a framework for trainers to develop high-quality training practices, taking into account the future impact on their audience. It consists of 5 stages:

- ENGAGE. The teacher attempts to grasp the learners' past knowledge and spot any knowledge gaps during the first stage of the learning cycle. In order for adult learners to be prepared to learn, it is also critical to spark their interest in the things to come.
- EXPLORE. Learners actively investigate the new subject through practical learning experiences throughout the exploration phase. To make observations, they might be required to follow the

scientific method and interact with their peers. This stage enables hands-on learning for adult learners.

- **EXPLAIN.** Learners are guided by educators during this phase as they synthesise new information and ask questions if they need further explanation. Before providing knowledge more directly in the Explain phase, trainers should invite learners to discuss what they discovered during the Explore phase. In order to improve understanding, educators may also use video, computer software, or other tools at this time.
- **ELABORATE.** Providing learners with the opportunity to put what they have learned into practise is a key goal of the 5E Model's elaboration phase. They gain a greater understanding as a result. To reinforce new abilities, trainers could urge students to make presentations or carry out further research. Before being evaluated, this stage enables learners to solidify their knowledge.
- **EVALUATE.** The 5E Model supports formal and informal evaluation. Teachers can watch their learners throughout this phase to determine whether they fully understand the fundamental ideas. Observing whether students approach situations differently as a result of what they learnt is also beneficial. Exams, writing projects, and peer evaluation are additional beneficial aspects of the Evaluate phase.

Considering the framework of both above-described design instructional models, the research has been conducted in 5 different stages, with a clear involvement of the project target groups:

1. **Primary research:** researchers have conducted the design and analysis of a survey distributed to adults 55+ from Romania, Spain and Turkey, in order to outline the way learners learn. From data collected through the survey, partners were able to further analyse and validate a list of real requirements for adult educators.
2. **Desk research:** the project team members searched for successful practices of digital pedagogies at national and European levels. With this activity, researchers worked on the identification and understanding of teaching methods, tools and instruments adapted to educators' needs, through the collection of success cases and existing initiatives that support digital literacy and learning of adult learners and seniors, as well as their educators.
3. **Competence map and self-assessment tool for digital educators:** the research team identified the specific knowledge, skills, abilities and behaviours required by digital educators to create engaging and active learning, highlighting the mismatch between previously assessed educational needs and competences required to address the prior, to operate effectively in online and offline adult education. So, transnational research teams summarized the most needed competences required by adult educators, so as to allow conceiving the competence map for digital educators of adults 55+. A transnational co-creation workshop was a key element for the fulfilment of this stage.
4. **Tools for digital facilitators of adults 55+:** a collection of tools and instruments was assembled by the research team and structured to mirror the competence map. The role of this toolbox is to assist digital facilitators of adults 55+ in rounding their knowledge, attitudes and skills in the six areas that compose the competence map. It is thought that these will further assist field educators in designing and delivering digital courses.
5. **Reviewing and concluding:** finalising the above-described stages of the project research phase was accompanied by the review of the relevant deliverables. Upon collecting feedback from

researchers and adult educators, final refinements were done, which cleared the way for publishing the current manual and sharing it with potential users.

The following chapters further expand upon the above-mentioned stages and outcomes.

Chapter 2. The readiness of adult learners for digital transformation

As a solid basis for the Digital Facilitator for Adults 55+ Toolkit, surveying the indirect recipient of it (adults over 55 years old) was essential. In fact, in order to properly equip educators of adult centres and the working staff seemingly related to adults 55+, it has been useful to know how these adults learn and approach technology, and how they behave in the digital environment.

Researchers from Formative Footprint (Spain), TEAM4Excellence (Romania), Voluntariat Pentru Viata (Romania) and Saricam Halk Egitimi Merkezi (Turkey) contributed to the development and implementation of the survey, for the analysis of the adult learners' readiness of the digital media in their surroundings. They set a series of questions and choice answers with the overall rationale of providing useful data on the research topic. Competence mismatches and digital teaching practices ideas emerged, that further facilitated a more complete design and structure of the competence map.

Every project partner undertook the following actions, all of which those being functional for the analysis fulfilment:

- Translations of the questionnaires in the national language;
- Dissemination of the surveys at local, regional and national levels;
- Assurance of anonymity of respondents for personal data elaboration;
- Collection and analysis of the information received;
- Reporting and translating the surveys' answers;
- Review and storage of the corresponding deliverable.

The six-question survey was therefore a quantitative and qualitative data research, aiming to obtain a full understanding of the digital education gaps and most common digital habits of the surveyed group of adults, so as to set a starting point for the applicability of certain teaching/learning digital practices.

The questionnaire was launched in June and closed in July 2022. During 30 days, 150 responses were collected from adults 55+ from the adherent project countries. The limited number of respondents was selected as adequate and trustful for research purposes, with a low margin of error. This way, the survey became an asset for the overall development of the project result.

The detailed findings section summarizes the responses received from the respondents. The set of questions addressed the perception of the adult learner towards the digital environment approach and their engagement with it, as well as the sense of trustability when using ICT. An open question was introduced to invite the respondents to give written suggestions on how to reduce the mismatch between what is taught and what it is needed to be learnt, and for sharing relevant experiences of digital behaviour.

Analyzing the responses, it was concluded that the respondents:

- Still struggle with understanding the functionality of the digital environment (46%);
- Daily digital activity is based on video-calling and messaging (78%);
- Prefer the "learning by doing" method, including training by practising the newly acquired skills (82%);
- Trust an educator to let them know about ICT and how to use those (91%).

2.2 Methodology

From the combination and application of the ADDIE and 5E model of instructional design above described, researchers conducted a survey made up of 5 closed questions and 1 open, for the duration of 30 days (from the 15th of June to the 15th of July 2022), in 3 different countries (Romania, Spain and Turkey), involving a total of 150 adult learners over 55 years old. The researcher leader proposed a series of questions that, over some discussion, were confirmed to be the following:

1. *How would you define your relationship with a digital device?*
 - Conflictual
 - Easy
 - I do not use any digital device.

2. *What is your daily digital activity about? (multiple choices).*
 - Videocalls with siblings and friends, and messaging;
 - Shopping;
 - Games;
 - Social networks (including dating apps);
 - Necessary mobile apps (for medical appointments, banking, shared transports, etc.)
 - Training (whether physically or mentally through specific apps for physical exercise or memory, for instance)
 - Reading online newspapers;
 - Working;
 - Learning a foreign language;
 - None of the above listed.

3. *How have you learnt to do the above-chosen digital activity?*
 - A sibling taught me;
 - I took a course about digital literacy;
 - I've learnt by attempts.

4. *Would you trust an adult educator's expertise in the field of ICT and eventually learn from him/her?*
 - Yes
 - No

5. *Select the sentence that better suits your way of learning about anything (multiple choice).*
 - I like learning by doing;
 - I need theory before any practical activity;
 - I learn by heart, so I won't need to understand how things I have to learn work;
 - I love playing and learning through that;
 - I better learn inside a group of people, from mutual exchange;
 - I learn in a one-to-one situation.

6. *Is there any suggestion on how to improve the teaching process of digital literacy? (brief paragraph).*

The original English survey was shared in a Google Form, from where translation into Romanian, Spanish and Turkish were edited, and so disseminated through links to informal local partners and stakeholders of the project partners, emails, social networks (Facebook mainly) and private messaging (Whatsapp, Messenger).

Once finalized, the surveys' answers have been compared and reported through graphics where it can be appreciated the ratio of the research.

2.3 Research results

The following paragraphs report the distribution of the 150 respondents in percentage for each survey question.

1. *How would you define your relationship with a digital device?*

- **Conflictual 40%**
- **Easy 54%**
- **I do not use any digital device 6%.**

2. *What is your daily digital activity about? (multiple choices).*

- **Videocalls with siblings and friends, and messaging 78%;**
- Shopping 30%;
- Games 18%;
- **Social networks (including dating apps) 41%;**
- **Necessary mobile apps (for medical appointments, banking, shared transports, etc.) 44%**
- Training (whether physically or mentally through specific apps for physical exercise or memory, for instance) 16%
- **Reading online newspapers 49%;**
- Working 30%;
- Learning a foreign language 13%;
- None of the above listed 3%.

3. *How have you learnt to do the above-chosen digital activity?*

- **A sibling taught me 30%;**
- **I took a course about digital literacy 8%;**
- **I've learnt by attempts 62%.**

4. *Would you trust an adult educator's expertise in the field of ICT and eventually learn from him/her?*

- **Yes 91%;**
- **No 9%.**

5. *Select the sentence that better suits your way of learning about anything (multiple choice).*

- **I like learning by doing 82%;**
- I need theory before any practical activity 20%;
- I learn by heart, so I won't need to understand how things I have to learn work 1%;
- I love playing and learning through that 15%;
- **I better learn inside a group of people, from mutual exchange 33%;**
- **I learn in a one-to-one situation 18%.**

6. *Is there any suggestion on how to improve the teaching process of digital literacy? (brief paragraph).*

- **Enhanced practical training 31%;**
- **Use of accessible images and tools 13%;**

- Intensive and efficient work 7%;
- Qualified trainers 9%;
- Attention to students' needs 7%;
- Fighting fears of the unknown 4%;
- **Online course accessible to all 13%;**
- On-site courses 7%;
- State-funded courses 4%.

Is there any suggestion on how to improve the teaching process of digital literacy?

Analysis of positive answers

2.4 Analysis of findings

The survey respondents highlighted a lot about the average adult learner over 55.

In the first instance, the sense of conflict felt by these respondents showed a real need for proper motivating digital facilitation. What is more, when it comes to analysing the usage of those respondents who stated their relationship with ICT as “easy”, their main digital activities seem to be circumscribed to messaging, social networking mainly, video calling and taking appointments, which reveal a certain distance from a digital behaviour at learning and educating service.

As for the role of the educator, it has been clear that adult’s basic digital education has been facilitated by the practice of technology itself, or by family components, supposedly digital natives.

This data, together with the answers about the trustability of educators who would teach about digital skills, knowledge and attitudes, shows a small amount of reticence in the adult learner. In fact, through the contributions that 37% of respondents wrote, it was possible to understand that the surveyed concern is based on the training delivery methods and better-prepared trainers.

Accessibility and practical training seem to be the best-valued ways for adults 55+ to make knowledge and skills attractive and effective to be learnt. Personalization of the teaching methodology also seems to be an interesting feature for adult learners, especially if that flexibility encounters their real learning needs.

2.5 Conclusions and recommendations

The survey showed the need for trustable and qualified personnel in adult education centres, especially when adults, with different study and work backgrounds, have to learn about a very conflictual topic.

All the results created from this research should be open and susceptible to transferability.

A change in the vision towards digitalization has to be promoted among adult 55+ learners: being online and digitally present is not only about social networking or messaging. This transition has to be always more clear in the teaching/learning service, with guided consecutive levels of competence and acquirable subsequent degrees of expertise.

Source: picpedia.org

Chapter 3. Good practices for digital pedagogies

Partners researchers approached the research of digital pedagogical practices through instructional design models (ADDIE, 5E), and yet defined the national digital educational environment where the 55+ adult educators operate, as a useful need analysis assessment.

3.1 Identification of good practices

Researchers identified the best digital teaching practices based on a common set of criteria:

- Effectiveness (in line with stated learning objectives);
- Inclusiveness (all learners can participate fully in their learning);
- Innovation (integrates new tools and technologies);
- Transferability (may be applied to similar situations).

As for the content of the research itself, partners focused their attention on digital pedagogical practices and methods that would allow the adult to acquire those digital skills to access support services, medical appointments, welfare activities and to stay safe online.

3.2 Methodology collecting good practices

Researchers reported the tools and instruments by completing a template (Appendix), that allowed them to point out the following common data and information about the identified practices:

- Name
- Description
- Key Stakeholders/Provider
- Level (Organizational, Regional, Local, National)
- Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)
- Skills acquired or enhanced
- Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)
- Tools/Resources/Services
- Link/ Website.

Once collected, the research leader proposed an analysis of those practices, that allowed the researchers to highlight tools and instruments among the collected ones from the perspective of instructional design. By comparison among all results, project partners set a common ground for further interactions with the involved target groups.

3.3 Good practices collection

With the following listed good practices, it is introduced how adult education addresses the digital transition. It is an overview of the existing digital instruments and tools that equip educators to face the educational need of 55+ adults for digital literacy at the current moment.

Among the collected practices, it is possible to notice partial or full adherence to the educational competence frameworks (EU DigComp and DigCompEdu) and/or other programs with different topics treated through ICT.

Good practice 1. Expertclick

<i>Name</i>	Expertclick
<i>Description</i>	Expertclick offers training in new technologies to people over 55 years of age, especially from rural areas. In the free face-to-face and online courses, the elderly learn to safely and confidently navigate the Internet and to use their mobile phone or tablet to communicate by videoconference, do business with their bank, request a medical appointment, buy online or take advantage of their leisure time creative online.
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	Cibervoluntarios Foundation and the AEB Foundation of the Spanish Banking Association (AEB), with the support of the Ministry of Social Rights and the 2030 Agenda.
<i>Level</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	Fighting the fear of the elderly about technologies.
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increased independence and personal autonomy; • communication; • carrying out procedures and actively participating in society; • improving their self-esteem and promoting active and healthy ageing.
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statistics, if available)</i>	https://expertclick.org/#experiences
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Training programme
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://expertclick.org/#project

Good practice 2. CapaciTIC55+

Name	CapaciTIC55+
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>CapacitaTIC+55 accompanies adults over 55 in their active job search process and therefore in their job training. It includes basic abilities and skills for job search: Curriculum Vitae, letter, interview, use of job portals, etc., and acknowledgement of the Internet, Google and Windows.</p> <p>Presential training includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electronic Administration Workshop 1: Cl@ve System and the Citizen Folder; • Workshop Electronic Administration 2 and Online Banking: Digital certificate and electronic ID; • Contact Workshop. Communication tools. WhatsApp and Videoconferences; • Mobile Handling Workshop: Most common uses; • Mobile Applications Workshop: Most used applications.
<p><i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i></p>	<p>Inciso, Castilla y La Mancha Region, co-funded by the European Commission.</p>
<p><i>Level</i></p>	<p> <input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> National <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> International </p>
<p><i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i></p>	<p>Job search for unemployed adults with no digital skills</p>
<p><i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication; • Administration; • Flexibility.
<p><i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i></p>	<p>900 people trained in 2020</p>
<p><i>Tools/Resources/Services</i></p>	<p>Training programme</p>
<p><i>Link/ Website</i></p>	<p>https://www.capacitatic55.com/index.php</p>

Good practice 3. Videoatención

<i>Name</i>	Videoatención
<i>Description</i>	The Videoatención Service is based on the use of a video communication system installed on seniors' television and connected to the Internet, which enables them to hold a videoconference with the Attention Center and carry out a series of activities Individuals aimed at exercising various cognitive areas: memory, praxis, gnosis, language, executive function and calculation with the support of volunteers who lead the session. Videoatención is conceived as a dynamic, flexible, attentive service that is close to the reality and needs of the people it is aimed at, which is why the Red Cross works in a participatory manner with the users so that the service is adapted and responds to your particular needs at all times.
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	Cruz Roja Española, Vodafone
<i>Level</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	To prevent cognitive deterioration associated with age and/or maintain the physical, cognitive and relational abilities of the elderly, with the support of new technologies.
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication; • Memory; • Language; • Calculation.
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	Reduced feelings of loneliness among the participants of the service.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Service, socio-sanitary attention.
<i>Link/ Website</i>	http://www.cruzroja.es/teleasistencia/eus/teleasistencia-videoatencion.html

Good practice 4. Proyectos TIC

<i>Name</i>	Proyectos TIC. Fotografía para la tercera edad
<i>Description</i>	This project is aimed at elderly people. It consists of a photography workshop, through which these people are going to tell a story through photos in order to have the possibility of learning with new technologies through the Internet.
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	Educación Social de la Universidad de Granada and their students
<i>Level</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	Lacking freedom of expression among unheard seniors and boosting their talents and digital skills through amateur photography.
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creativity; • Artistic expression; • Digital editing.
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	The project gives voice to older people since considered to be the least listened to in society, and this workshop allows them to have their means of expression. Wide exposure of the photographs is a key success factor.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Project-based on training
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://edusougr.wordpress.com/2013/05/12/proyectos-tic-5/

Good practice 5. Kahoot, Mentimeter, Geochaching

<i>Name</i>	Kahoot, Mentimeter, Geochaching
<i>Description</i>	<p>These are just some of many mobile applications that adult centres use for getting seniors more active as well as their classes and workshops on digitalization.</p> <p>Kahoot! Play & Create Quizzes: is a digital learning platform that uses quiz-style games to help students of all ages learn by making the information engaging in a fun way. It's also a helpful tool for a hybrid class that uses both digital and classroom-based learning.</p> <p>Mentimeter: easy-to-build presentations, interactive Polls, Quizzes, and Word Clouds mean more participation and less stress.</p> <p>Geochaching: a game of outdoor hide-and-seek is a great way to break up seniors' day and get them moving outside. It's entertaining for all ages, and many seniors enjoy geocaching with family members or friends to share the fun.</p>
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	Formative Footprint (uses it in daily workshops)
<i>Level</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> National <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	All the above-listed apps prevent isolation, lack of physical movement and deterioration of seniors' minds.
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical exercise; • Memory; • Language.
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	These apps have millions of participants using those per year.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Online tools
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://kahoot.com/ https://www.mentimeter.com/ https://www.geocaching.com/play https://www.tailoredhomecareinc.com/featured/geocaching-for-seniors/

Good practice 6. Digital Spring applications

<i>Name</i>	Digital Spring applications
<i>Description</i>	Digital Spring, a social responsibility project, aims to help older adults live a healthier life by providing them with a sports program that they can do at home.
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	The Ministry of Family and Social Services & Turkcell (major telecommunication and technology services provider in Turkey). The target group of this project is older adults.
<i>Level</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	<p>First and foremost, it was implemented with applications for those residing in nursing homes in order to alleviate the negative feelings caused by the pandemic period.</p> <p>For the first time in Turkey, the Digital Spring Project brings sports programs to homes for older adults and enables them to stay healthy and fit with home exercise program content.</p>
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adults can access brand new activities with the opportunities brought by technology. • In the video content, in which dozens of different exercises are explained in detail, many physical movements that are beneficial for adults are shown in the company of sports trainers.
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	It continues to demonstrate the equalizing power of technology by expanding the scope of the Digital Spring Project, which aims to add value to the lives of older adults through innovative technologies.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Training Videos
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://www.turkcell.com.tr/dijitalbahar

Good practice 7. Digital Spring technology rooms

<i>Name</i>	Digital Spring technology rooms
<i>Description</i>	<p>Digital Spring, a social responsibility project, aims to increase the digital literacy of the elderly living in nursing homes affiliated with the Ministry of Family and Social Services.</p> <p>Technology rooms have been established in ten nursing homes in three years as of 2021, where the elderly can use and experience technology. Based on the results, the Ministry of Family and Social Services aims to expand the Project to all nursing homes across the country in the coming years.</p> <p>In the technology rooms created within the scope of the project, which was initiated in nursing homes in Ankara and Istanbul as a pilot region, the elderly have the opportunity to communicate with their families and friends in the digital environment and with plus reality technology, as well as travel the world with virtual glasses, make new friendships and get to know the digital world.</p>
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	<p>Ministry of Family and Social Services & Turkcell (major telecommunication and technology services provider in Turkey). The target group of this project is the elderly.</p>
<i>Level</i>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International</p>
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	<p>The goal was to benefit from the healing power of technology to bring spring to the elderly living in nursing homes and to eliminate the negative feelings caused by the pandemic period.</p> <p>Under the auspices of the Ministry of Family and Social Services, technological equipment and appropriate, comfortable living and experience areas that connect them to life are being created in nursing homes across Turkey.</p>
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tablets are available in every nursing home. The elderly are able to video call with their loved ones and play digital games on their tablets. • They are able to use the Bip Meet cabin to make private video calls with their families.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With TV installed, they are able to watch movies, series and TV content, as well as make synchronous video calls with computers from the large TV screen. • They are able to listen to timeless songs and all current songs in Fizy corner via Bluetooth speakers. • With VR, they are able to visit places they wouldn't normally visit. • Activities such as online quiz competitions, technology and device training, backgammon tournaments, and knowledge transfer meetings with young people are organized in the rooms, and special projects for their socialization are implemented. • On the platform, Digital Literacy online training program is also available for the elderly (meet the digital world with the digital literacy program). <p>Digital Literacy training program consists of 4 stages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Computer and Internet Usage: Fundamentals of computer and internet world • Mobile Application Usage: Smart devices and mobile applications • Social Media Usage: Social media platforms and usage • Word Tutorial: Basics of Microsoft Word application.
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	After completing Digital Literacy Online Training Program and passing the exam, it is possible to qualify for a certificate. So far, over 7000 people have received certificates.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	https://gelecegiyazanlar.turkcell.com.tr/konu/dijital-okuryazarlik#courses_list
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://www.turkcell.com.tr/dijitalbahar

Good practice 8. Digital Literate project

<i>Name</i>	Digital Literate Turkey Project (Dijital Okuryazar Türkiye (DOT) Projesi)
<i>Description</i>	Digital Literate Turkey, a social responsibility project, aims to increase the use of digital banking for people over the age of 65, who are the age group most affected physically and emotionally by the Covid-19 process. Furthermore, the Digital Literacy Turkey project aims to bring together studies and training in this field with citizens in order for them to adapt to the change and transformation experienced through smart phones, computers, and smart devices.
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	The Digital Marketing Communication Platform (DMIP) was created by the Advertisers Association, Interactive Advertising Association and Mobile Marketing Association(MMA). The target group of the project is adults 65+.
<i>Level</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	<p>With the advancement of technology and digitalization, the importance of digital literacy has grown. Individuals must be digitally literate in order to keep up with the times and use digital devices effectively.</p> <p>With sponsorship from Akbank, Garanti BBVA, Türkiye İş Bankası, and Yapı Kredi banks, the first DOT project, in line with the Digital Turkey mission, was designed on the digital and financial literacy of older adults.</p>
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<p>The elderly can access awareness videos and training on topics such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Shopping • Online Savings • Online Money Transfer • Online Payments • E-Government Access • Online Account Opening.
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	The Digital Literate Turkey (Dijital Okuryazar Türkiye - DOT) Project provides free digital and financial literacy training to people aged 65 and up across Turkey.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Online Training
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://www.dijitalokuryazarturkiye.com/

Good practice 9. Digital Literate pilot training

<p><i>Name</i></p>	<p>Digital Literate Turkey Project (Dijital Okuryazar Türkiye (DOT) Projesi)</p>
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>A pilot training was conducted to improve the lives of citizens over the age of 65 within the scope of the Digital Literacy Turkey Project, which was initiated as a social responsibility project. The training aimed to improve the skills of the participants in video calling, sending location, online banking, online shopping, use of social platforms, and use of critical sites such as e-government and e-pulse.</p>
<p><i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i></p>	<p>Yeditepe University, Yarenlik Platformu, Mobil Marketing Association Turkey (MMA). The target groups of the project are adults 65+ and young people.</p>
<p><i>Level</i></p>	<p> <input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International </p>
<p><i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i></p>	<p>It is aimed to contribute to the adaptation of people aged 65 and over to digitalized life. As part of the project, undergraduate and graduate students from Yeditepe University E-Commerce Department were trained on "how to deliver digital literacy education" to adults over the age of 65. Each student was paired with a friend responsible for the education of an elder.</p>
<p><i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i></p>	<p>The participants received training on the university campus every Saturday for 10 weeks and sometimes online due to the pandemic conditions. The training included the topics in the following.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Banking Applications • Zoom Video Conferencing Training • Migros Virtual Market Training • Whatsapp Application Tutorial • E-Government Application Training • E-Pulse Application Training • Glossary of Digital Literacy Terms

<p><i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i></p>	<p>The Pilot training started in 2021 by Yeditepe University in cooperation with MMA, was developed by DMIP and spread throughout Turkey as of 2022.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In 2021, 2000 people were reached online. ● During severe pandemic conditions, the elderly had the opportunity to improve their social relationships and perform transactions that made their lives easier, such as digital banking, online shopping, calling relatives via video calls, and taking photos. <p>To develop the project and begin Stage 2, Yeditepe University collaborated with Yarenlik Platform, which already works with people over the age of 65, and MMA Turkey, which started a similar project.</p> <p>"Digital Literate Project E-adapt" Stage II began on March 26, 2022, with volunteer students from Yeditepe University Faculty of Commercial Sciences E-Commerce Management Department. Every week until the end of the semester, volunteer students were provided various digital training to the elderly online.</p> <p>The Digital Literate Turkey Project carries on with new participants. More people of all ages will be reached as education staff is increased and collaboration with municipalities throughout Turkey is established.</p>
<p><i>Tools/Resources/Services</i></p>	<p>https://e-adaptasyon.com/egitimler/</p>
<p><i>Link/ Website</i></p>	<p>https://e-adaptasyon.com/</p>

Good practice 10. The lifelong learning portal

<p><i>Name</i></p>	<p>The Lifelong Learning Portal</p>
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>In January 2018, the Ministry of National Education (MoNE) launched The Lifelong Learning Portal, which allows citizens of all ages to access lifelong learning activities from a single location. As ‘the door to learning and working opportunities’, the portal is a significant innovation. The portal provides lifelong guidance on information for people's professional and personal development needs, in addition to current learning and employment opportunities. The Portal, which brings together data from various service providers, provides information on all learning opportunities, from basic education to higher education, non-formal education to distance learning.</p> <p>The courses that provide lifelong skills, knowledge, and cultural development to individuals of various ages at Public Education Centres (PECs) affiliated with the Ministry of National Education are the most common of these training courses. These courses are offered free of charge on a regular basis throughout the year. At the district and neighbourhood level, these courses are accessible to all segments of society. PECs provide educational activities for people of all ages, including the elderly.</p>
<p><i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i></p>	<p>MoNE, PECs.</p> <p>The target groups of the program can be adults, elderly, young people and trainers/educators.</p>
<p><i>Level</i></p>	<p> <input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International </p>
<p><i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i></p>	<p>PECs, as one of the primary providers of non-formal education, organize digital and ICT skills training programs for the elderly, as well as training programs for educators on the use of digital tools in learning environments.</p>
<p><i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i></p>	<p>ICT Courses at PECs</p> <p>PECs in Turkey provides a wide range of courses to the elderly including ICT courses.</p>

	<p>Nursing homes may also request courses for their residents, and small-group training may be provided. PECs lead this practice as a part of their annual programme and curriculum.</p> <p>This practice aims to provide basic ICT skills to the elderly to help them meet their needs, such as using bank applications, communicating with relatives and loved ones and finding information online. Teachers/trainers provide group training in computer labs. Hands-on activities are used to ensure that the elderly can put what they learn into practice.</p> <p>Some of the courses available include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Literacy (Basic Level) Training Program • Digital Literacy (Intermediate Level) Training Program • Media Literacy Training Program
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	The quality and timeliness of the information on all learning opportunities are key success factors.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Training Programs
<i>Link/ Website</i>	www.hbo.gov.tr

Good practice 11. Papa Pals

<p><i>Name</i></p>	<p>How to teach technology to seniors – Papa Pals</p>
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>Papa Pals offers tech help for older adults and families. He offers advice about how to explain the value of technology, address security concerns, emphasize internet safety, write about her work, give them confidence, guide them to free resources, adapt devices to meet their physical needs and help them keep their skills sharp.</p> <p>This platform can be used online and this aspect is very easy to access.</p>
<p><i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i></p>	<p>The target groups for this project are teachers, adults, the elderly and students. Each of them wants to improve their digital knowledge.</p>
<p><i>Level</i></p>	<p> <input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International </p>
<p><i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i></p>	<p>A problem which was solved with the help of this program is communication online with young people. Another problem solved was finding health information online.</p>
<p><i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i></p>	<p>With the widespread use of technology amongst seniors, some may still need a helping hand when it comes to anything from using their SmartTV to navigating the Web or using a new app on their smartphone.</p> <p>Fortunately, tech help for seniors is easy to find. Not only do Papa Pal caregivers understand tech, but they also have the patience to teach anyone how to use it effectively.</p> <p>Over time, the elderly can easily communicate with their grandchildren or children. Older people can more easily find information on topics that interest them.</p>
<p><i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i></p>	<p>A 2019 study from Pew Research about seniors and technology use found that 73% of adults ages 65 and older use the internet. That number is up from just 14% in 2000.</p> <p>Plus, 53% of Americans 65 and old Another Pew Research study shared that 58% of adults ages 65 and older say</p>

	technology has had a “mostly positive” impact on society, while one-in-ten of senior Internet users say they are online “almost constantly” or own a smartphone.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Medicare.org published a list of free computer classes for seniors. Local libraries and senior community centres may also offer courses in tech for seniors. YouTube is a great resource to learn whatever apps your senior loved ones may want to learn how to use.
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://www.papa.com/resources/blog/how-to-teach-technology-to-seniors

Good practice 12. Optimizing tech for older adults

<p><i>Name</i></p>	<p>Optimizing tech for older adults</p> <p>Psychologists are helping to study, design, and adapt all kinds of technologies to make them intuitively understandable for older adults</p>
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>This program wats to improve the skills of the elderly. They started with a research space. The space looks like a roomy, ultramodern house outfitted with the latest smart technology and gadgets, including smart refrigerators, ovens, digital assistants, home sensors—even coffee makers. The facility also includes an independent control room where researchers can simulate remote activities like telehealth, as well as an innovation lab and classroom space.</p> <p>One major focus for psychologists in the area is developing home-based technologies to make life easier, safer, and more interesting for older adults. CHART is at the cutting edge of this work, bringing together faculty and students in community health, psychology, engineering, architecture, public health, and other disciplines to design and study technologies for successful ageing.</p> <p>Because the pandemic has made it unsafe, we propose to work with robots. In one set of projects, researchers are testing robots to perform tasks of daily living.</p>
<p><i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i></p>	<p>The target groups for this project are adults and the elderly in particular. Each of them wants to improve their digital knowledge.</p>
<p><i>Level</i></p>	<p> <input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International </p>
<p><i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i></p>	<p>One problem that has been solved is for the elderly alone, with the help of this program they have learned to use video conferencing or to speak with a virtual assistant.</p> <p>On the other hand, this project talks about robots that can do some household chores, handle by the elderly.</p>
<p><i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i></p>	<p>With the widespread use of technology amongst seniors, some may still need a helping hand when it comes to anything from</p>

	<p>using their SmartTV to navigating the Web or using a new app on their smartphone.</p> <p>Fortunately, tech help for seniors is easy to find. Not only do Papa Pal caregivers understand tech, but they also have the patience to teach anyone how to use it effectively.</p> <p>Over time, the elderly can easily communicate with their grandchildren or children. Older people can more easily find information on topics that interest them.</p> <p>This program wants to promote safe driving. Some researchers use technology to study the best ways to enhance driving safety among older adults, including in automated vehicles.</p>
<p><i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i></p>	<p>According to studies, the elderly are sometimes as proficient as younger adults at some tasks. For example, Feng thought older drivers might have more difficulty and be slower in assuming control of automated vehicles than younger drivers. But “they were equally good at taking over, and they didn’t really show inferior capability,” she said. Older people are very receptive when it comes to digital skills.</p>
<p><i>Tools/Resources/Services</i></p>	<p>For this project, they must use human resources like psychologists and material resources like a laboratory for different experiments. The robots can be tested in the laboratory.</p>
<p><i>Link/ Website</i></p>	<p>https://www.apa.org/monitor/2021/07/tech-older-adults</p>

Good practice 13. ICT Skills 4All and ICT4TheElderly

<p><i>Name</i></p>	<p>ICT Skills 4All and ICT4TheElderly</p>
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>This program aims to improve the lives of older adults by teaching them digital skills and introducing them to various online tools and possibilities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICT Skills 4 All – Empowering old citizens for a digital world aims at fostering digital skills, self-confidence and online safety of old adults aged 55 years and over who have minimal or no engagement with digital technology. <p>In order to do so, the ICTSkills4All project has developed an ICT Learning Programme, which includes:</p> <p>A dedicated online platform with information, training tools and resources addressed to those who have low digital skills;</p> <p>Face-to-face support using the inter-generational and peer-to-peer approach is addressed for those who have no digital skills.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICT for the Elderly – project aims at enhancing the digital skills of the elderly, creating awareness about Internet use among the elderly and their communities and networking and capacity-building of project partners and stakeholders involved.
<p><i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i></p>	<p>The target groups for this project are the elderly, maybe can be the students for their knowledge. Each of them wants to improve their digital knowledge.</p>
<p><i>Level</i></p>	<p> <input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International </p>
<p><i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i></p>	<p>Issues that have been resolved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning digital terms Be careful with security Communication through online platforms.
<p><i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i></p>	<p>At the end of the program they must be able to:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train elderly people to develop the digital skills needed to access public services online • Provide a tailored solution for overcoming barriers related to access, skills, confidence and motivation of elderly people to take full advantage of the opportunities offered by the internet and digital services • Apply a confidence-building approach by developing virtual assistance based on elderly people’s real-life scenarios
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	According to studies, the elderly are sometimes as proficient as younger adults at some tasks. They have the desire to learn more about technology because most of the time they are alone. This technology can help them to be happy and relaxed and to see the family from a distance. Older people are very receptive when it comes to digital skills.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	For this project, they must use human resources like trainers and material resources like laptops and the internet.
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://www.simplonromania.org/2020/06/22/seniori-in-era-digitala/

Good practice 14. Simplon

<p><i>Name</i></p>	<p>Simplon - Serious in the digital time</p> <p>This program encourages online general education sessions, conducted in the form of a contest on an online platform.</p> <p>The hosts of these meetings are the Simplon Romania trainers.</p>
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>This program wats to improve the skills of the elderly. They started with an online platform. Within this platform appeared online sessions about general culture. The elderly are helped by Simplon Romania trainers. They want the elderly to feel relaxed and to know that here they can find answers to their technical issues.</p> <p>The meetings were initially weekly, and now take place every two weeks.</p> <p>After that, they developed a facebook group called "Seniors in digital times". In this group are involved youth volunteers with technical knowledge who want to help. On this platform, the areas of interest are voted before the online meetings, details are discussed, and the following sessions are established.</p>
<p><i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i></p>	<p>The target groups for this project are the elderly, maybe can be the students for their knowledge. Each of them wants to improve their digital knowledge.</p>
<p><i>Level</i></p>	<p> <input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International </p>
<p><i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i></p>	<p>One problem that has been solved is for the elderly alone, with the help of this program they have learned to use video conferencing or to speak with other people.</p> <p>On the other hand, this platform provided help to the elderly not only to use the computer but also the telephone.</p>
<p><i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i></p>	<p>The Digital Seniors program was the one that stimulated seniors' interest in learning how to operate a computer and use the Internet. Thus they demonstrated that they can adapt to new technologies and that the ability to learn does not refer to a certain age.</p>

	After a few sessions, the seniors managed to use the applications on the phone, facebook or other communication applications.
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	According to studies, the elderly are sometimes as proficient as younger adults at some tasks. They have the desire to learn more about technology because most of the time they are alone. This technology can help them to be happy, and relaxed and to see the family from a distance. Older people are very receptive when it comes to digital skills.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	For this project, they must use human resources like trainers and material resources like laptops, and the internet.
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://www.simplonromania.org/2020/06/22/seniori-in-era-digitala/

Good practice 15. Candoo Tech

<i>Name</i>	Candoo Tech
<i>Description</i>	<p>Candoo Tech is an online service which provides tech support and training specifically designed to help older adults use technology to stay safe, secure and engaged.</p> <p>The training sessions and device installation help centre are online. Candoo Tech is providing nationwide remote tech consultation, support and training to customers who are 65+.</p>
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	<p>The target groups for this project are adults and the elderly in particular. Each of them wants to improve their digital knowledge.</p>
<i>Level</i>	<p> <input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International </p>
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	<p>Candoo wants to help adults to improve their skills and to make their life easier in this way. The problems addressed here are also about their health and financial status. More adults with tech skills mean increased economic opportunities for underemployed populations. One of their other goals is to improve the health and well-being of older adults by decreasing social isolation and giving them a sense of community and connectedness.</p>
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<p>While Candoo can come for an a la carte visit to install new devices or solve a specific problem, most users sign up for an annual membership. Priced at \$240, the membership covers unlimited remote support by phone or online and two free in-home visits to introduce additional devices or apps to the client, provide further training or troubleshoot a particularly sticky problem.</p> <p>Seniors need to be receptive to the advice and training they receive. They must be persevering to acquire advanced skills if the level from which they started is low. Unlike traditional tech support services that focus on fixing specific, user-identified problems, Candoo Tech takes a holistic approach to tech support, identifying the needs of a client, introducing tech-based solutions and providing clients with ongoing support so</p>

	<p>seniors can develop proficiency with new devices and tools at their own pace.</p> <p>Developing a basic fluency with film and TV streaming services like Netflix and watching programming on an iPad or other tablet might seem daunting at first, but open up a galaxy of entertainment options beyond daytime TV.</p> <p>Password manager programs have proven incredibly useful for keeping users of all ages online, connected and secure, but are particularly important for older users, who are often seen as easier targets for malicious hackers.</p> <p>Social online games like Words With Friends are a fun activity for seniors that can help encourage mental activity and social engagement, keeping families and social circles close regardless of physical distance.</p>
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	<p>Founded in 2019, Candoo Tech is a for-profit PBC (Public Benefit Corp) based in New York. Candoo is a proud member of the Techstars Future of Longevity Accelerator in partnership with Melinda Gates' Pivotal Ventures.</p>
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	<p>Candoo provides online sessions, online membership and device installation setup. An online session means one hour with a tech specialist to fix what's not working with users' phones, computers, or tablets, or to teach them something new. Online membership is for training, where tech specialists can teach you how to use technology or a particular device, install software and answer quick questions. The device Installation and Setup service is designed for consultation in matters of choosing devices or software according to needs.</p>
<i>Link/ Website</i>	<p>https://www.candootech.com/</p>

Good practice 16. Digital literacy for seniors

<i>Name</i>	Digital literacy for seniors
<i>Description</i>	The ECDL EqualSkills program runs for 20 hours. At the end of the program, participants can obtain ECDL EqualSkills certification. Through “Digital Literacy for Seniors”, ECDL ROMANIA together with its partners actively contributed to achieving the objectives of the European Digital Agenda, marking the context of the European Year of Active Aging and Solidarity between Generations (AEIA 2012). Advantages of “Digital Literacy for Seniors”:
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	ECDL ROMANIA
<i>Level</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	Fighting the fear of the elderly about technologies.
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration in the information society; • Obtaining an internationally recognized certification; • Attestation of acquired digital skills; • Increasing self-confidence; • Socialization and new ways of communication; • Stimulating personal initiative, regardless of age and social status; • Computer use for a variety of needs, including e-commerce and e-government services; • Increasing the quality of life of the participant; • Discovering new ways of spending free time.
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statistics, if available)</i>	https://ecd.ro/articol/alfabetizare-digitala-pentru-seniori_115.html
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Training programme
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://ecd.ro/articol/campanii-ecd-romania_16.html

Good practice 17. DInSAd board game

<i>Name</i>	DInSAd board game
<i>Description</i>	<p>An interactive board game that enables low-skilled adults 55+ to acquire basic digital knowledge, skills and competencies.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A learning methodology through play and four specific tools, a board game, the development of Guides for mentors/study circle leaders, 20 adults with a low level of commitment in testing the board game four mentors/study circle leaders engaged in testing the game four national validation reports and one European Validation Report.
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	Digital Inclusion of low skilled adults
<i>Level</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	The game aims to strengthen the ability of adults 55+ to use effectively digital tools as a prerequisite for improving one's personal life and thus significantly reducing the trend of the intergenerational digital divide.
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To use effectively digital tools
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	The participants were very determined to use the card game because they acknowledged that the game allowed them to practice skills they did not have.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Training programme
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://www.dinsad.eu/images/results/DInSAd_Game_Instructions_RO.pdf

Good practice 18. Digital skills map

Name	Digital skills map
<i>Description</i>	A Digital skills map is a specific key digital skill required by low-skilled adults to improve their quality of professional and personal life. Sixteen best practices were selected, and twenty interviews (5 / country) with key actors interested in adult digital education and their social inclusion through the use of digital tools for their daily lives. A map of digital competences according to EQF and DigComp, four national focus groups with relevant actors for the validation of the competence map, four national validation reports and a European validation report
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	Digital Inclusion of low skilled adults
<i>Level</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	<p>The authors consider that this document could have a relevant impact on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improving the quality and diversity of learning opportunities available to low-skilled adults; 2. Supporting the European Commission in implementing DigComp 2.1 for all European citizens, regardless of their age and/or level of education; 3. Disseminate the concept of digital inclusion at both professional and personal levels for low-skilled adults in Europe; 4. Increasing transparency and recognition of competences.
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital inclusion • Increasing transparency and recognition of competences
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	In Romania, the participants did not discuss so much about the competencies contained in the Digital Competence Map, but rather, how adults can acquire these skills and use them in their professional life, or daily. This is in a way understandable, as not all teachers, but rather managers of public or private bodies dealing with low-level adults in terms of needs and expectations

<p><i>Tools/Resources/Services</i></p>	<p>Search and download online news about movies, books, readings, museums, and music. Find information about travel schedules (plane, train, bus), availability of seats, availability of holidays, hotel occupancy, etc. Try to install and use one application.</p>
<p><i>Link/ Website</i></p>	<p>https://www.dinsad.eu/images/results/DInSAdO1-A2_Definition_of_digital_competences_for_adults_short_ro.pdf</p>

Good practice 19. Media literacy

<i>Name</i>	Media literacy
<i>Description</i>	Adults 55+ are equipped with tools which help them to critically analyze the messages. The module provides also various opportunities to expand their experience in media and help them develop creative skills in making their own media messages. The adults become familiar with different types of information to be able to select the most reliable source of information. They become able to critically evaluate and raise awareness of the risks posed by the new media.
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	Digitalise me
<i>Level</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	Cyber-bullying
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying the reliability of information sources • Media manipulation • Media literacy vs. online security
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	The development of awareness and critical thinking skills of adults 55+ are key success factors.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Project-based on training
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://digitaliseme.eu/ro/course-module/6

Good practice 20. Super Lingo

<i>Name</i>	Super Lingo
<i>Description</i>	<p>Super Lingo describes a specifically tailored, modern, online English-language learning project incorporating a set of interactive vocabulary games and role-playing scenarios for continued practice. Learning new vocabulary helps retain memory. Role-playing is a commonly used language learning exercise which gives students a chance to activate their knowledge in a safe setting. This is a particularly relevant methodology for our target audience of older adults who may have transportation issues, auditory or other health problems, and who tend to process new information at a slower rate and so require more repetitions than provided in traditional learning settings. The recorded relevant content can be listened to as many times as needed. The games will be based on memory practice such as memory card games, putting letters in the right place, hangman etc. Moreover, the adult learners are able to continue practising their newly learned language skills in a safe and convenient environment which will encourage long-term use and increase their cognitive reserve in the process.</p>
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	Asociatia Habilitas
<i>Level</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	<p>The Super Lingo project is intended to improve and extend the supply of high-quality learning opportunities which are tailored to the needs of people experiencing cognitive decline and mild dementia. This will be assured by creating an innovative foreign language training program tailored to this target group. A team of language, technology and dementia experts will work with our target population on a continuous basis establishing feedback loops to design, test and refine the training package</p>
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role play games • Memory games • Library • Seminars • Workshops

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiplier events • Dissemination activities • Informal meetings • Social media
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	The interdisciplinary team of experts is a key success factor.
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	Online tools
<i>Link/ Website</i>	https://www.habilitas.ro/index.php/en/super-lingo-2/

3.4 Analysis of good practices

As mentioned in the identification of the good practices and methodology paragraphs, researchers followed the instructional design ADDIE and 5Es models in order to assure that the shared practices address the project-highlighted needs and target groups' problems, fulfil the project objectives, and, as such, all of those allow to design, develop, implement and assess the digital competences of the good practice's recipient (adults 55+).

The analysis indicated a strong transferability potentiality of all the described practices: educators and adult education centres staff are so provided with a ready-to-be-tested package of projects/ programmes/ instruments suitable for adaptation and re-usage. As for those practices involving telecommunication companies (nos. 3, 6, 7, 15), educators are advised to search for the same type of endorsement to achieve a more effective application of the practice. Nevertheless, with the local help of stakeholders with a similar provider's role, it would be possible to equip the community with the most inclusive and innovative tools that allow basic services for adults 55+.

Source: PMWorld360.com

What appears to be transversal to the overall collection, whether the illustrated practice has a governmental or an organizational basis, is the intention of promoting lifelong learning at the adult's digital empowerment service. As it is evident, researchers searched and select practices that are meant to make the life of the adult individual easier through technology's full understanding.

It has to be noted, that in the case of practices targeted to elderly people, the latter is also meant to embrace very specific purposes, such as providing medical assistance and social presence, so as to avoid further problems linked to isolation. Communication and inclusion, in all their diverse manifestation, can be considered the leitmotif for many of the analysed practices.

Digital Facilitators, by adapting and reusing these collected practices favouring online and offline training, have the mission to positively engage adult learners and clean up their vision of demonized technology. In fact, as follows with the competence map in the next chapter, it becomes clearer the importance of the role of the educators, from creating attractiveness in technologies to commit the learners towards their usage, and even being able to provide feedback through and about those.

Chapter 4. Competences of digital facilitators for adults 55+

Being a digital facilitator requires having a set of specific skills, knowledge, abilities and behaviours enabling digital educators to operate effectively in online and offline adult education. According to the DigCompEdu, there are six main areas relevant for digital facilitators, namely: Professional Engagement, Digital Resources, Teaching and Learning, Assessment, Empowering Learners and Facilitating Learners' Digital Competences (Redecker 2017).

Source: adapted from Redecker 2017

From the examples of good practices across Europe and the survey which collected information from adults 55+, the research team concluded that adults 55+ have specific non-formal education needs. Moreover, they have specific preferences on how to learn, which are determined by their status. For this reason, the good practice programmes, projects and activities are rightfully tailored specifically to adults 55+.

To advance the lifelong learning and integration of adults 55+ in society and to ease their transition from employment to retirement, the entire educational construct needs to be adapted compared to other age groups. This educational construct includes, for example, answering fundamental questions such as: what topics are being addressed, where the training activities take place, when or for what period and, most importantly, how the training and non-formal education is being designed and delivered. The answer to these questions rests with the adult education providers but, ultimately, with their trainers and facilitators who work directly with adults 55+.

The Covid-19 pandemic restricted to a great extent many facilitators and trainers from organising face-to-face activities. Therefore, during the pandemic period, they had to deliver their non-formal education activities in hybrid or online modes. This implied using digital tools which required them to learn how to design and deliver activities using digital tools but also to train adults 55+ on using those digital tools. Overall, the profile of trainers changed from facilitators to digital facilitators. As was shown in the precursory primary and secondary research, this fundamental change did not start from the ground level but benefited from the existing tools and experiences of employing digital tools in the educational process. However, these changes required a significant upgrade of the digital competences of adult educators.

One of the lessons learnt during the pandemic was that there are many benefits of digitalising non-formal education. Going forward, with the ease of the pandemic, it is expected that the digital knowledge, attitudes and skills gained by both adults 55+ and their adult educators will not only be retained but will be further developed and expanded upon. However, as the current research showed, digital facilitators of adults 55+ need a specific competence map, tools to assess their current competence across the competence map and the resources to improve their digital competences.

In this chapter, we focus on the competence map and the self-assessment instrument designed by the research team to identify competence gaps in the six areas set out by the DigCompEdu framework, while a collection of tools which assist digital facilitators of adults 55+ in bridging those gaps is included in the next chapter.

4.1 Competence map

As previously set out, the precursory research and the associated analysis of results sought to inform the definition of a specific competence map for digital adult facilitators of adults 55+, based on the more general existing DigCompEdu framework. The specific competence map which is presented in this chapter took into consideration the fact that digital facilitators may need different competences while working with different target groups. Indeed, for those trainers or observers who participated in training courses with participants from different age groups, it may seem obvious that a training course with young people would look and feel different from a training course with mid-age adults or adults 55+. Even if the same topic is being addressed, the focus, non-formal education methods, instruments, digital tools and course materials are expected to be different.

Considering the above, a specific competence map was designed by the research team. It includes six areas, each of these with several pin-point items. The map is presented below, while each area is further expanded upon and explained thereafter.

PROFESSIONAL ENGAGEMENT

- Digital CPD (stay up to date about the digital transition)
- Professional collaboration (active listening, sharing educational practices)
- Organisational communication (suitable tools for TG, simple language)

DIGITAL RESOURCES

- Selecting digital resources (to be used with adults)
- Creating and modifying digital resources
- Managing, protecting and sharing digital resources

TEACHING

- Teaching (pedagogical knowledge and skills, patient attitude)
- Guidance (adjusted to target groups)
- Collaborative learning (communication among all the parties)

ASSESSMENT

- Assessment strategies (tools, make sure the content has been applied, standardisation of evaluation criteria)
- Feedback and planning (personal assessment, self-reflection, personalisation, formative assessment, level of satisfaction for further content improvements)

EMPOWERING LEARNERS

- Actively engaging learners (learning by doing, propose interactivity, motivation, teamworking)
- Accessibility and inclusion (adapting content and guaranteeing participation for all age target groups, provide networking)
- Differentiation and personalisation (splitting the content in different levels or versions)

FACILITATING LEARNERS' DIGITAL COMPETENCES

- Information and media literacy (organize, identify, analyse and store information and digital content)
- Problem solving (find alternatives to the learning process, risk management strategy)
- Responsible use (independent and safe conception of using digital resources, making them understand the associated risks)

Professional engagement

Professional engagement of digital facilitators means, without pretending to be an exhaustive list, collecting digital CPD, being part of a professional network, listening and sharing educational practices, and also using communication tools to remain in touch with your peers and learners.

Professionally engaged digital facilitators for adults 55+ are committed to the goal of using digital tools to make their professional life easier. They are constantly updating in respect to digital transition, which is a crucial feature for educators who wish to grow in their work. They identify their own digital learning needs and analyse, evaluate and expand their pedagogical teaching resources. They appreciate the opportunities to engage with their learners inside and outside physical and virtual classrooms, while they encourage active listening and enrich the educational environment of learners using as many digital resources as possible. To maximize learning, professionally engaged educators develop skills in organizational communication, using simple language and adapting teaching tools to the adults 55+ target group. They are eager to support other educators in implementing technologies in their classes, as well as in their working team, for a better-organized environment.

Digital resources

Using and accessing digital resources area of competencies focuses on selecting proper digital resources to be used in adult learner education, creating and modifying digital resources, as well as managing, protecting and sharing digital resources.

Digital resourced facilitators for adults 55+ are able to search and select digital reliable teaching content, adaptable to diverse target audiences. They are aware of the consequences of the violation of intellectual property and use digital material protected by copyright or licenses wisely. They know how to edit existing digital content for teaching purposes, especially in relation to the learners' needs and according to their digital literacy level. They have a positive attitude towards the creation of original educational content, by using available and well-known digital tools, as well as avant-garde platforms and apps. They are concerned to warrant quality for every digital material they produce. They encourage learners to communicate through online tools for educational purposes, including properly sharing edited and original content when allowed.

Teaching and learning

This area emphasizes the need for digital facilitators of adults to have pedagogical knowledge and skills as well as a patient attitude to guide the learners in accordance with their needs. In addition, a collaborative learning environment can enhance communication among all parties.

Digital facilitators of adults 55+ must be endowed with an attitude of patience, adaptability, creativity and, above all, provided with pedagogical knowledge and skills. Only by nurturing connections and building relationships with learners through technologies, they are able to guide the target group and encourage them to collaborative learning, introducing digital elements into teaching. Perfect facilitators are the ones who can exploit a digital environment to enhance knowledge, skills and attitude of their own and their learners. They are concerned about the effectiveness and appropriateness of the digital pedagogical strategies chosen to deliver the conveyed formative content. Teachers foster a co-design learning process, mostly possible through an aware usage of digital tools, which boost collaborative learning activities, and participatory apprenticeship.

Assessment

Assessment strategies and application of a variety of tools and instruments make sure the content is being applied and is relevant. Digital facilitators use a standardization of evaluation criteria, collect feedback and analyse the results, to be able to compare and make informed decisions regarding the integration in practice. Moreover, the digital facilitators are planning the assessment including personal assessment, self-reflection, personalization, formative assessment and level of satisfaction for further content improvements.

Digital assessors find a like to combine and evaluate data generated by digital technologies used. Their assessment skills are based on enhancing their teaching style through the usage of digital tools, including the attitude of making sure that the delivered content has been properly internalized by the learners. They are eager to plan the feedback to be received learner-wise, putting high concern on self-digital-development and personal competence through the usage of technologies for teaching purposes. Moreover, the criteria assessors establish for the evaluation of the learning outputs, created through the implementation of technologies, are aimed at personalizing their teaching performance and improving content and feedback, based on the data generated by the digital technologies used.

Empowering learners

Empowering means: Actively engaging learners (learning by doing, proposing interactivity, motivation and teamworking), Accessibility and inclusion (adapting content and guaranteeing participation for all TG ages, providing networking), and Differentiation and personalization (splitting the content into different levels or versions).

Learner empowerers are motivated to actively engage learners to be part of the overall digital acknowledgement and skilling process. They are concerned about the learners' access to technologies, including the learners' literacy to have the competence to use those, and their different digital learning needs. They usually design several learning pathways, levels and speeds when creating, selecting and implementing digital learning activities. They stand by the non-formal education imperative of „learning by doing/learning by playing”, which guarantees a stimulating and always interactive digital learning environment, and constant discovery of innovative educational tools. They are really up to embellishing hard-to-be-treated topics through multimedia resources, which engages learners while getting competent.

Facilitating learners' digital competences

Educators facilitate the learners' digital competencies: Information and media literacy (organize, identify, analyze and store information and digital content), Problem-solving (find alternatives to keep the learning process, risk management strategy), Responsible use (independent and safe conception of using digital resources, make understand the risks of those).

Digital Competence Facilitators know how to teach learners to find information and assess its reliability. They like to design learning activities that allow the learner to search, identify, analyse and select the data and content they need, through suitable digital technologies and sources. They usually motivate the learners towards their independency in the digital environment, developing always a higher level of digital literacy, especially throughout the edition, creation and sharing of multimedia material of their own. The Digital Competence Facilitators foster problem-solving activities, which make the learners develop abilities to handle risks, attitudes to use technologies responsibly, and

knowledge to report threatening online behaviours and to guarantee the best digital learning experience.

4.2 Competence self-assessment tool

The competence map which was presented previously assists digital facilitators in understanding what competences they need to be able to design and deliver training to adults 55+ in the digital era. Once they have a round picture of the competences they need, then they can actively engage in developing those skills, starting from what they know towards what they should know. But knowing what we know is not always that straight forward and many fail to understand their current level of competence in various areas and therefore are not able to make those steps necessary to develop themselves and evolve. To overcome this, the project research team created the competence self-assessment tool which is described below.

The DIFA 55+ competence self-assessment tool designed and implemented by the research team took input from the DigCompEdu framework (in terms of the six areas of competence), the primary and secondary research carried out and included in this manual (in terms of specific competences for digital facilitators of adults 55+), the Learning Styles Questionnaire (LSQ) designed by Peter Honey and Alan Mumford (in terms of the questionnaire design) and the existing online questionnaire option of the Moodle Course Management System (CMS), a free open source software package designed to help educators create and deliver effective online courses. The Moodle self-assessment tool created in this project also rests on the previous works of TEAM4Excellence project coordinators in the Erasmus+ Strategic partnership to develop open educational resources for teaching digital citizenship (DIGCIT), ID 2019-3-RO01-KA205-078053 (Acomi et al 2022). In that project, TEAM4Excellence advanced the ways in which Moodle technology can successfully be utilized in designing online self-assessments.

The DIFA 55+ competence self-assessment tool provides digital facilitators for adults 55+ with the opportunity to map their existing competences across the six areas of competences which we identified and expanded upon above. The tool rests on a package of 30 questions, five questions for each of the six areas. Each question designed by the research team is situational, asking respondents to think about what they do in practice. The multiple-choice answer options are Yes or No.

In essence, the DIFA 55+ tool is a perception competence measurement instrument, since answering Yes or No to a situational question about what they do in practice is a matter of personal choice. Therefore, it is important that respondents are true to themselves, but this is inherent for all those who wish to take a self-assessment to see where they excel and in which area they could improve.

As a result, the DIFA 55+ competence self-assessment tool not only helps respondents to find out how they map across the six areas of competence but also how they compare with their peers across those six areas. This feature is enabled in the Moodle self-assessment in the results and feedback area.

The following headings include the questions designed for each competence area with the applicable scale (very strong/strong/moderate/low/very low) and the feedback received by respondents on the completion of the self-assessment process. Finally, a distinctive heading is dedicated to the online version of the self-assessment tool and instructions for users.

Professional engagement

Questions

1. I setup meetings using digital technologies.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. I search the Internet for professional development opportunities.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

3. I use the Internet to discover new pedagogical methods and strategies.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

4. I communicate with other educators via digital technologies.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

5. I assist other educators in gaining digital pedagogical competence.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

Answer

You have a (very strong/strong/moderate/low/very low) preference for “Professionally Engaged”.

Professionally engaged digital facilitators for adults 55+ are committed to using digital tools to make their professional life easier. They are constantly updating with respect to digital transition, which is a crucial feature for educators who wish to grow in their work. They identify their own digital learning needs and analyse, evaluate and expand their pedagogical teaching resources. They appreciate the opportunities to engage with their learners inside and outside physical and virtual classrooms, while they encourage active listening and enrich the educational environment of learners using as many digital resources as possible. To maximize learning, professionally engaged educators develop skills in organizational communication, using simple language and adapting teaching tools to the adults 55+ target group. They are eager to support other educators in implementing technologies in their classes, as well as in their working team, for a better-organized environment.

Digital resources

Questions

1. I filter results when I search digital resources for teaching and learning.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. I critically evaluate the credibility and reliability of digital sources and resources.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

3. I am aware that some materials made available online are protected by copyright.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

4. I modify and edit already-existing digital resources, where that is allowed.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

5. I produce new digital educational resources.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

Answer

You have a (very strong/strong/moderate/low/very low) preference for “Digital Resourced”.

Digital resourced facilitators for adults 55+ are able to search and select digital reliable teaching content, adaptable to diverse target audiences. They are aware of the consequences of the violation of intellectual property and use digital material protected by copyright or licenses wisely. They know how to edit existing digital content for teaching purposes, especially in relation to the learners' needs and according to their digital literacy level. They have a positive attitude towards the creation of original educational content, by using available and well-known digital tools, as well as avant-garde platforms and apps. They are concerned to warrant quality for every digital material they produce. They encourage learners to communicate through online tools for educational purposes, including properly sharing edited and original content when allowed.

Teaching and learning

Questions

1. I facilitate teaching in a digital environment.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. I interact with learners in collaborative digital environments.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

3. I analyze the effectiveness and appropriateness of the digital pedagogical strategies chosen.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

4. I use digital tools that allow learners to design their own learning (e.g. blogs, diaries, planning tools).
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

5. I implement collaborative learning activities in a digital environment (e.g. using blogs, wikis, learning management systems).
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

Answer

You have a (very strong/strong/moderate/low/very low) preference for “Digital Teaching”.

Digital facilitators of adults 55+ must be endowed with an attitude of patience, adaptability, creativity and, above all, provided with pedagogical knowledge and skills. Only by nurturing connections and building relationships with learners through technologies, they are able to guide the target group and encourage them to collaborative learning, introducing digital elements into teaching. Perfect facilitators are the ones who can exploit a digital environment to enhance knowledge, skills and attitude of their own and their learners. They are concerned about the effectiveness and appropriateness of the digital pedagogical strategies chosen to deliver the conveyed formative content. Teachers foster a co-design learning process, mostly possible through an aware usage of digital tools, which boost collaborative learning activities, and participatory apprenticeship.

Assessment

Questions

1. I enhance formative and summative assessment strategies through digital technologies.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. I consider, combine and evaluate data generated by digital technologies used.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

3. I adapt my teaching and evaluation techniques, based on the data produced by the digital technologies I use.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

4. I provide feedback based on the data generated by the digital technologies used.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

5. I reflect on which teaching strategies work best for different types of learners, using the data produced by digital technology, and I adjust my methods as appropriate.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

Answer

You have a (very strong/strong/moderate/low/very low) preference for “Digital assessment”.

Digital assessors find a like to combine and evaluate data generated by digital technologies used. Their assessment skills are based on enhancing their teaching style through the usage of digital tools, including the attitude of making sure that the delivered content has been properly internalized by the learners. They are eager to plan the feedback to be received learner-wise, putting high concern on self-digital-development and personal competence through the usage of technologies for teaching purposes. Moreover, the criteria assessors establish for the evaluation of the learning outputs, created through the implementation of technologies, are aimed at personalizing their teaching performance and improving content and feedback, based on the data generated by the digital technologies used.

Empowering learners

Questions

1. I ensure that all students have access to the digital technologies used.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. I consider the students with special needs when creating and using digital tools and teaching methods.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

3. I take into account different learning pathways, levels and speeds when designing, selecting and implementing digital learning activities.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

4. I use interesting and stimulating digital learning environments and activities (e.g. games, quizzes).
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

5. I use digital technologies to show and explain new topics in motivating and engaging ways (e.g. by employing animations or videos).
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

Answer

You have a (very strong/strong/moderate/low/very low) preference for “Learner Empowerment”.

Learner empowerers are motivated to actively engage learners to be part of the overall digital acknowledgement and skilling process. They are concerned about the learners’ access to technologies, including the learners’ literacy to have the competence to use those, and their different digital learning needs. They usually design several learning pathways, levels and speeds when creating, selecting and implementing digital learning activities. They stand by the non-formal education imperative of „learning by doing/learning by playing”, which guarantees a stimulating and always interactive digital learning environment, and constant discovery of innovative educational tools. They are really up to embellishing hard-to-be-treated topics through multimedia resources, which engages learners while getting competent.

Facilitating learners' digital competence

Questions

1. I teach learners how to find information and assess its reliability.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. I include learning activities that require learners to share data, information and digital content with others through suitable digital technology.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

3. I encourage learners to edit and create new, original and relevant digital content.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

4. I react immediately and effectively when learners' well-being is threatened in digital environments (e.g. cyberbullying).
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

5. I implement problem-solving tasks that are solved through digital technologies.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

Answer

You have a (very strong/strong/moderate/low/very low) preference for "Digital Competence Facilitator".

Digital Competence Facilitators know how to teach learners to find information and assess its reliability. They like to design learning activities that allow the learner to search, identify, analyse and select the data and content they need, through suitable digital technologies and sources. They usually motivate the learners towards their independency in the digital environment, developing always a higher level of digital literacy, especially throughout the edition, creation and sharing of multimedia material of their own. The Digital Competence Facilitators foster problem-solving activities, which make the learners develop abilities to handle risks, attitudes to use technologies responsibly, and knowledge to report threatening online behaviours and to guarantee the best digital learning experience.

The self-assessment tool in action using Moodle

The following paragraphs and the associated images present the DIFA 55+ self-assessment tool in action using Moodle. In its online version, the platform calculates and displays in a radar plot the levels of competence on a 0 to 100% scale by competence area in intervals of 20% (very strong/strong/moderate/low/very low). Moreover, the platform generates a radar plot for the entire cohort of respondents, so that each respondent can compare himself/herself with others. In the following, the authors explain the step-by-step process of using the platform, explaining how it works.

Reaching the Moodle platform

The self-assessment tool was operationalized into the [TrainingClub.eu](https://trainingclub.eu) European Nonformal Education Online Platform developed by TEAM4Excellence with support from the Erasmus+ programme to foster online education across Europe. The platform includes free courses and self-assessments for educators and learners of all ages. Users can browse and audit the courses as guests. The DIFA 55+ self-assessment tool is included in the Personal Development Assessments category.

With updates and upgrades of Moodle, plugins and content, the platform may look different at various points in time, but the structure and the way it works are likely to remain the same.

Auditing the DIFA 55+ self-assessment tool

Having reached the Personal Development Assessments category, users can read the general description.

Having done so, users can then enter and audit the DIFA 55+ self-assessment tool. Should they wish to proceed with taking the self-assessment, they should first register on the platform and then enrol on the self-assessment.

Need to go to the login page

Creating an account and enrolling on the self-assessment

Registering into the platform requires creating a new account. Those already registered into the platform will skip registration and will proceed with logging in using the user name and password, their email or Facebook accounts.

Creating an account requires filling in all the required fields and following the link received in the given email account. If the registration email is not in their Inbox, then users should check the Spam folder.

Once registered, users can Enroll:

Taking the self-assessment

Taking the self-assessment requires participants to scroll down and respond with Yes or No to 30 questions.

QUESTIONNAIRE
Self-assessment quiz

Digital Facilitator Skills - Competence map [Print Blank](#)

1. I setup meetings using digital technologies.
 Yes No
2. I search the Internet for professional development opportunities.
 Yes No
3. I use the Internet to discover new pedagogical methods and strategies.
 Yes No
4. I communicate with other educators via digital technologies.
 Yes No
5. I assist other educators in gaining digital pedagogical competence.
 Yes No

Upon answering all questions, click submit. If one or more questions remain unanswered, then the platform will prompt users, indicating the unanswered question(s). Answer the remaining questions and click Submit again.

24. I use interesting and stimulating digital learning environments and activities (e.g. games, quizzes).
 Yes No
25. I use digital technologies to show and explain new topics in motivating and engaging ways (e.g. by employing animations or videos).
 Yes No
26. I teach learners how to find information and assess its reliability.
 Yes No
27. I include learning activities that require learners to share data, information and digital content with others through suitable digital technology.
 Yes No
28. I encourage learners to edit and create new, original and relevant digital content.
 Yes No
29. I react immediately and effectively when learners' well-being is threatened in digital environments (e.g. cyberbullying).
 Yes No
30. I implement problem-solving tasks that are solved through digital technologies.
 Yes No

[Submit questionnaire](#)

Getting results and feedback

Upon successfully completing the self-assessments, respondents will be provided with results. The results will include a tabular percentage score for each competence area, a personal radar plot competence map and the competence map generated by the platform based on the answers of the entire cohort of respondents.

In addition to the above, users will be provided with descriptions for each of the six areas, so they can relate the score to the specific competences for digital facilitators included in the competence map.

Feedback Report

You have a very strong preference for "Professionally Engaged".

Professionally engaged digital facilitators for adults 55+ are committed with the goal of using digital tools to make their professional life easier. They are constantly updating with respect to digital transition, which is a crucial feature for educators who wish to grow in their work. They identify their own digital learning needs and analyse, evaluate and expand their pedagogical teaching resources. They appreciate the opportunities to engage with their learners inside and outside physical and virtual classrooms, while they encourage active listening and enrich the educational environment of learners using as many digital resources as possible. To maximize learning, professionally engaged educators develop skills in organizational communication, using simple language and adapting teaching tools to the adults 55+ target group. They are eager to support other educators in implementing technologies in their classes, as well as in their working team, for a better-organized environment.

You have a very strong preference for "Digital Teaching".

Digital facilitators of adults 55+ must be endowed with an attitude of patience, adaptability, creativity and, above all, provided with pedagogical knowledge and skills. Only by nurturing connections and building relationships with learners through technologies, they are able to guide the target group and encourage them to collaborative learning. Perfect facilitators are the ones who can exploit a digital environment to enhance knowledge, skills and attitude of their own and their learners. They are concerned about the effectiveness and appropriateness of the digital pedagogical strategies chosen to deliver the conveyed formative content. Teachers foster a co-design learning process, mostly possible through an aware usage of digital tools, which boost collaborative learning activities, and participatory apprenticeship.

You have a very strong preference for "Digital assessment".

Digital assessors find a like to combine and evaluate data generated by digital technologies used. Their assessment skills are based on enhancing their teaching style through the usage of digital tools, including the attitude of making sure that the delivered content has been properly internalized by the learners. They are eager to plan the feedback to be received learner-wise, putting high concern on self-digital-development and personal competence through the usage of technologies for teaching purposes. Moreover, the criteria assessors establish for the evaluation of the learning outputs, created through the implementation of technologies, are aimed at personalizing their teaching performance and improving content and feedback, based on the data generated by the digital technologies used.

Understanding and using the feedback

Knowing the current levels of competence is of crucial importance for all those who want to step up and improve their attitudes, knowledge and skills, particularly in the weakest areas. But knowing where you are may not be enough. Understanding the textual feedback provided lays the foundation for actively using the feedback towards competence development.

Nevertheless, digital facilitators who wish to better their competences in the subject area need the relevant resources/tools and proper guidance for each of the six competence areas. These are provided in the next chapter.

Chapter 5. Tools for digital facilitators of adults 55+

In the previous chapters, the project researchers and adult educators developed a research methodology, implemented it through primary research (survey) and desk research (finding and analysing good practices), fed the research into a competence map and developed an online self-assessment tool for digital facilitators of adults 55+.

At this stage, the project seeks to expand the research into the tools that may assist digital facilitators of adults 55+ in rounding their knowledge, attitudes and skills in the six areas that compose the competence map. It is thought that these will further assist field educators in designing and delivering digital courses. For clarity, in the scope of the current manual, digital courses include face-to-face, hybrid and online courses that employ digital technology to support the creation and delivery of non-formal courses for adults 55+.

The toolbox assembled by the research team and included below is structured to mirror the competence map. However, readers may note that many of these tools address more than one competence area. At the same time, the toolbox is far from being exhaustive but represents a good starting point for all adult educators in their attempt to improve their competences as digital facilitators for adults 55+.

5.1 Area 1 - Professional engagement

Coursera

[Coursera](#) is a global online learning platform that offers access to online courses and degrees from leading universities and companies. Coursera offers online courses, certificates, and degrees in a range of areas in collaboration with universities and other organizations.

Coursera collaborates with more than 250 top institutions and businesses to offer adaptable, accessible, and career-relevant online learning to people and organizations all around the world. The majority of courses are offered for free and they involve reading, participating in conversations with other learners, seeing lecture videos and presentations, and doing projects and tests. Coursera provides a variety of learning options, ranging from practical projects and classes to degree and certificate programs. Some courses (and groups of courses) are eligible for accreditation, however, it necessitates additional steps like paying fees and proving your identity on assignments. The good news is that you may study at these renowned colleges wherever you are, at your own speed.

We appreciate that the Coursera platform enables us to offer a variety of top-notch courses and a learning environment that our staff members may choose from to further their professional growth. With access to top colleges and reputable organizations on Coursera, you may prepare for a position at an entry-level, further your career with a certificate or degree, or upskill your team.

Harvard University Courses

[Harvard Online](#) offers carefully selected online courses that bring together professors and disciplines from throughout the university, connecting learners from across the world with the most pressing problems.

Learners get access to a wide range of courses through Harvard Online that are based on international knowledge and research. Curated course series expand learning possibilities by bringing together professors and disciplines from throughout the university. Each course was created by the Vice Provost for Learning Advances at Harvard (VPAL). By finding novel approaches to enhancing learners' competence, curiosity, and confidence on our campuses and throughout the globe, VPAL aims to change the future of education. As Harvard Online build tools, technologies, platforms and policies to lessen friction across the learning lifecycle, it also promotes inspirational ideas, connects a worldwide community of learners and creates engaging and scalable learning experiences.

Learn new skills, hone old ones, or brush up on your knowledge with just one Harvard course. It provides approximately 1,000 courses to help you achieve your objectives, whether you want to develop new skills, consider a career change or broaden your viewpoint.

Udemy

[Udemy](#) is an alternative if you're looking for a one-off course in a particular subject or skill set. It is an online learning site that provides over 130,000 different online courses which are both free and paid.

On Udemy, you may find courses on a range of subjects taught by experts from across the globe. It might be beneficial to browse the free courses, which do not include certificates of completion or access to the instructors directly. A typical Udemy course includes lifetime access to the material as well as hours of educational video lectures that may be viewed on TV, computers, or mobile devices. If a course is offered on Udemy, you can enrol anytime you'd like. View or listen to lectures, perform exercises, take notes virtually, download supplemental materials, and interact with trainers and fellow learners on the course material. Every course may be finished at whatever pace suits you because there is no set time restriction. Another interesting feature of Udemy is that the courses can be given as a gift with the "Gift this course" button on the top left side of the screen.

Have a look around Udemy if you've ever wanted to learn or better a skill but didn't know where to start (or couldn't get there). There's a good chance that someone can assist you in training in the comfort of your own home.

Video conferencing software

Bring all the groups together, connect and have meetings with individuals anywhere in the globe using a computer, tablet, or smartphone thanks to video conferencing software.

Video conferencing is being used in classrooms to offer courses, conferences, one-on-one and small-group tutorials, and more. Using the same tools that corporations and other organizations use to facilitate video meetings, video conferencing enables the communication between learners and adult educators or trainers to trainers. Typically, to do this, you'll need video conferencing software, a computer or mobile device to run and an internet connection. Some common features of video conferencing software are HD video, screen sharing, recording the meeting, live chat, breakout rooms, whiteboards, live reactions or background filters.

Choosing a video conferencing program that is intended only for educational use might be useful for educators, such as [Zoom](#), [Google Meet](#), [Skype](#), [Webex](#) and [Microsoft Teams](#).

Chalk

[Chalk](#) offers a free online lesson planner. Educators may use this planning board to plan and view even their whole school year while staying on the overall schedule. Chalk increases learner achievement by ensuring that the curriculum is delivered. Also, trainers may include standards and curricular requirements and keep track of them.

Chalk offers a unified framework to make sure your curriculum, instruction, and assessment are connected to the pertinent standards and linked with one another. By developing an integrated system, you can assist instructors to eliminate gaps and assure learner success by using data-driven insights to determine what is working well, what isn't, and why. Create classes using a cutting-edge, user-friendly editor. Incorporate documents, images, and videos to make your teaching more engaging. Create lesson templates to further reduce preparation time so you can begin teaching right away. What is more, you can share your lessons with colleagues. With a few clicks, get fantastic materials from your peers. Lessons may be shared and imported directly into your planner. You may easily save and PDF your courses for offline distribution.

Chalk enables you to identify not just what didn't work but also what isn't working now and what won't work in the future. You may decide quickly and intelligently on your curriculum and instruction to ensure that all trainees have the chance to achieve.

Trello

[Trello](#) is a visual project management and task-tracking application that gives your team the ability to manage any kind of project. Whether you're a team of 2 or 2,000, Trello can be customized for your goal.

Trello is a project management application that divides your work into boards. It allows you to quickly see what is being worked on, who is working on it and where it is in the process. Consider a whiteboard covered with sticky notes with lists of tasks written on each one for you and your team. Imagine that each of those sticky notes also included a space for comments and team collaboration, as well as photographs, documents, and attachments from other data sources. Also, the tasks can be assigned deadlines and other status-tracking data. They can also contain notes, which allow team members to track progress and specific people can be flagged for action and follow-up. What is more, Trello is often used for personal itineraries. This service has three pricing tiers. The free version of Trello includes a maximum of 10 boards, but there's no limit on how many lists or cards each board can have. File attachments are limited to 10 MB, though.

Trello is primarily used as a web app, but there is a mobile app version available, as well, so imagine being able to view that whiteboard from any computer through the web and taking it with you everywhere you go on your smartphone.

5.2 Area 2 - Digital resources

Canva

[Canva](#) is a free online graphic design tool that allows users to create professional designs, even if they have no previous design knowledge. There are thousands of free, well-made templates that can be changed with just a few clicks thanks to their drag-and-drop interface.

Use a pre-existing template or create your own that you may modify the background, shape, font, text and positioning. For instance, you may design and print out motivating posters that represent the course objectives, use cheerful colour schemes to keep learners' attention or make visual memory aids like picture collages and banners that they can link with particular ideas. Making lesson plans is one of Canva for Education's most effective uses. You may use Canva to depict mathematical, statistical and scientific topics as well as produce text, videos, presentations or image-based visualizations. Also, with Canva you can design and customize your worksheets and exercises. Build your own or choose from a range of existing templates. What is more, to better conceptualize and document their learning, learners may utilize Canva to design and construct their own learning portfolios, on their own or in groups of up to 10 people.

Canva's ability to elevate visual learning to a new level for learners and instructors to become "design thinkers" is one of its strongest features. Keep in mind that there are free video lessons on their website if you're new to graphic design and want to learn about branding or how to use Canva in a virtual classroom.

Prezi

[Prezi](#) is a web-based tool for creating presentations, an alternative to conventional slide-making software. Only Prezi enables you to make presentations that zoom, move, and are visually spectacular, grabbing and holding the attention of your audience regardless of the subject.

There are three main features of Prezi: presentation, video and design. You may select from a number of themes and add your own content too. Using Prezi Present, you can organize your information in a variety of ways with subjects and subtopics to make captivating presentations for your audience. Subtopics arrange details and expose material at precisely the correct time to maintain readers' attention. Topics present your main ideas. You can quickly convert it to a video with Prezi Video. You can even import your existing PowerPoint slide decks into an engaging and interactive video and give your content a new life. To discover the ideal visual for your video, you may add text, upload photos or search through the enormous collection of pictures, icons, GIFs and stickers. Interactive charts, reports, infographics, and maps that are simple to develop and help people remember information can be also done by Prezi.

Prezi is an effective tool for grabbing learners' attention and improving the learning environment in the classroom. Also, it motivates the instructor to use the internet frequently and be inventive while creating Prezi presentations.

iLovePDF

[iLovePDF](#) is a document management software that will help you manage your PDF file. iLove PDF offers a toolkit to merge, compress, split, convert, watermark, and unlock PDFs within seconds. This software is simple to use and free.

Users can merge two or more PDFs, split a PDF into different files, remove one or multiple pages, extract and organize them. Also, it compresses PDF files, edits, numbers the pages, watermarks and repairs damaged or corrupted files. Since the most recent edition of the PDF editing tool, iLovePDF, you are now able to decorate plain PDF files with happy emojis and hearts. Additionally, you may alter read-only texts with text, photos, shapes, symbols, and characters with iLovePDF's PDF Editor. Furthermore, it has a conversion function from JPG, Word, PowerPoint, Excel and HTML to PDF and

vice versa. What is more, iLovePDF can remove the password from a PDF or secure it with a password. Also, it allows you to convert or batch-convert your PDF to PDF/A and even sign your documents.

Even better, the files you want to process don't even have to be on the computer or other device you're using. You may import files directly onto our page from a Google Drive or Dropbox account, process them, and then save the results back to the cloud. In fact, since it helps you use less mobile data, this approach is ideal for using the iLovePDF App from your smartphone or tablet.

OER Commons

Open Educational Resources (OER) are instructional resources that may be freely used and reused without incurring any fees and without requesting permission. This may allow you to download material and distribute it to colleagues and learners. In some circumstances, you might be allowed to take a material, make some changes to it, and then repost it as a remixed work.

[OER Commons](#) is a public digital library of free educational materials. It was made to enhance curriculum, research, produce, and interact with educators throughout the world. The website serves as a network for teaching and learning resources and provides access to tools for curriculum alignment, quality assessment, social bookmarking, tagging, rating, and reviewing. To arrange all the materials and make it easier for you to discover what you need, OER Commons employs a number of categories and labels. The categories characterize different features of the resources, such as grade level, topic area, and material type. You may build a portfolio, review, tag, and rate items, as well as add your own work to the site when you register with OER Commons or one of our sites.

In order to offer a single point of access to the finest quality information from all around the world, OER Commons has formed partnerships with more than 500 significant content partners. Over 42,000 validated and fully indexed OER are available for users to search, assuring a high degree of resource relevance and discovery. Since they are "open", these materials may be used in educational settings, and many of them have Creative Commons licenses that enable them to be recycled, altered, and customized for a wide range of regional contexts.

GoogleDrive

[Google Drive](#) is a file-sharing service, like a virtual cloud, used to store, share and collaborate on files and folders from your mobile device, tablet, or computer. It includes services like Docs, Sheets, and Slides, which are all similar to Microsoft Office.

The fact that Google Drive is a free service is its biggest advantage. Learners just need to create a Google account in order to use it. Another great advantage of Google Drive is that Google automatically saves the documents as you work. Also, trainers may group their documents into folders based on particular subjects. Drive is an excellent tool for submitting assignments, too. Learners can turn in papers or other tasks by making a folder that is solely accessible to the teacher and the trainer may remark right on the page. For learners to fill out class forms and compile their replies into a spreadsheet, educators can also utilize the Forms service. Trainers may also use Drive to offer access to classroom materials like notes or supplemental readings because the service keeps everything on one server.

Google Drive is an excellent service that is used in various settings. This service may be incorporated into the classroom to reduce trainer desk clutter. Additionally, as more businesses use Google Drive, it can help learners get ready for the future.

Dropbox

[Dropbox](#) is a cloud storage service used to save files online and share them with others. It is simple, trustworthy, private and secure and it is the preferred option for storing and sharing your most crucial data.

All of your work has a home on Dropbox. Whether working alone or collaborating, you may save and share data, work together on projects, and implement your greatest ideas. It promotes cooperation, sharing and creation within the learners' team. As an illustration, you could create a lesson plan on your computer, post it on Dropbox, and have it synchronized to another device. Additionally, by sharing a folder with other eLearners, you may make knowledge visible to everyone. Create links quickly for any Dropbox file that you want to send over text, chat, or email. Recipients may click the link to see and download the file without having a Dropbox account. Anyone viewing your shared links may examine more than 175 different file kinds and provide comments without any additional software. What is more, Dropbox makes it simple to work on files across several devices. Dropbox's basic service is free of charge and provides 2 GB of online storage.

For teaching and learning purposes, Dropbox is a useful tool. Create a folder on Dropbox then put all the educational resources you wish to provide to your trainees there. You may create as many folders as you like and then share certain files as necessary.

5.3 Area 3 – Teaching and learning

Learning management system

LMS stands for Learning Management System. When applied in an educational environment, this software helps trainers overcome such challenges by using a cloud-based tool to collaborate, assign and complete homework/assignments, create and view course content and more.

An LMS is made to support someone in creating, managing, and offering online learning programs and courses. One of the finest aspects of learning management systems is that they turn into a consolidated platform with all the required course materials and they can update course plans as they go along, making the course flow smoother. Instructors are able to distribute resources to all learners simply by uploading them on the LMS. An effective learning management system promotes social learning and engagement so that learners may benefit from one another's knowledge. On an LMS, several group projects may be completed together. Learners may communicate on LMS offline discussion boards and meet for group study sessions. That being said, within a course, each learner may establish their own unique objectives, study in groups or alone and complete optional evaluations as needed. They can even share the displays of their own devices. Instructors

Common LMS platforms used in education are [Moodle](#), [Google Classroom](#), [Mindflash](#), [Schoology](#), [Blackboard Learn](#) and [Canvas](#).

Lumio

With the help of [Lumio](#), instructors can turn lectures into interactive, collaborative learning experiences that keep learners interested on their own devices and engage them on a whole new level.

The lessons are delivered whether the learners are learning in class, remotely, or on their own time. Start with your favourite content, including PDFs, PowerPoint files, Google Slides, YouTube videos, or a blank lesson. Then bring it to life by adding images, text, and embedded video. Enhance with customizable game-based activities, graphic organizers and much more. You can also find thousands of ready-made resources directly within Lumio, including lessons, templates, and digital manipulatives. You can even record instructional audio right in your web browser that learners can play back as many times as they like for guidance and support anywhere, anytime. Furthermore, connect learners and spark collaboration, even at a distance, with whole-class or small-group collaborative activities with a shared canvas. Learners work together and contribute with text, images, ink, web links and more. They can do it simultaneously in class and remotely.

Guide them through your lesson, or let learners explore at their own pace, and easily change delivery modes at any time with the push of a button. Learners work on their own copy of the activities, while you observe and give feedback in real-time using the activity's dashboard. After the project is finished, you and your learners can review it.

Kialo

[Kialo Edu](#) is a large argument mapping and discussion website which is made exclusively for use in classrooms. Kialo's goal is to encourage thoughtful dialogue online and intellectual engagement.

Kialo is the best platform for distance learning since it enables trainers to take their classroom discussions online. The way the platform operates is by breaking down arguments into pro and con columns, each having sub-branches. Arguments are ranked by users, and as a result, move up or down the list. The idea behind Kialo is that it not only plans discussions, but also does it in a way that enables others to come in at any time and still understand where the conversation is at, what has happened, and how they might participate. Kialo provides for instructor moderation, which includes giving learners comments on their concepts, argumentation and research calibre. But ultimately, the choice of what constitutes a strong argument rests with the learners. Impact voting, which increases or lowers a point in accordance, is used to accomplish this. In order to facilitate group study, planning, and online debates, trainers might divide their learners into teams.

Kialo helps learners grow in confidence and the ability to interact on other subjects both online and in the real world. What is more, Kialo is completely free. Trainers may use the debating platform right away by just signing up online and inviting their learners to participate.

Screencastify

With [Screencastify](#) instructors may record crucial online moments that will ultimately improve learning and save time. Screencastify lets you record your tab, the entire screen, or your webcam and make educational films. Add your voice and face to personalize it and have Google Drive automatically save it. It is simple to install, use and operate on most devices.

You must first install Screencastify by choosing "Add to Chrome" after downloading the extension from the Chrome Web Store (which opens in a new tab) while using the Chrome browser. The Screencastify symbol will appear after installation in the upper right corner of your Chrome browser close to the address bar. Once you've selected the Screencastify icon in the Chrome browser you can launch the app. Screencastify allows you to draw on the screen to better clarify what you're talking about, such as within a browser tab. Screencastify features let you screen everything you are doing on the computer. For example, an option allows you to highlight your cursor, adding a bright circle around the icon. It's a bit like a laser pointer on a real-world blackboard. This can help learners better see what you're drawing attention to as you move the cursor around the screen.

What is more, Screencastify can be used for feedback too. You can create screencasts of your learners' work and record yourself commenting on them, or you can create videos while you check your learner's work and provide feedback along the way. You can also use the annotation tools to direct the focus onto specific aspects.

Padlet

[Padlet](#) is a free online tool that is best described as an online notice board. Learners and instructors can publish notes on a shared page using Padlet, such as links, videos, photos and document files.

This bulletin board stored in the cloud is quite similar to Pinterest. It is unique since it is ideally suited for collaboration. Everyone may collaborate, distribute, and share information on one platform, including learners, adult educators, and business owners. Users may publish and embed all kinds of digital content on Padlet because of its incredibly user-friendly design. In some aspects, Padlet is comparable to a notebook where you can collect pictures, text, documents, and videos to share with anyone, anytime, and on any device. If you're an educator, for instance, your learners may gather resources for a project and upload them there. To finish the assignment, you and your learners will be able to examine and apply all the material acquired.

Everything may be shared with a certain group, made public, or kept secret. This is only one of the features geared at educators that demonstrate how the product was developed with instructors' and learners' needs in mind.

Miro

[Miro](#) is the online collaborative whiteboard platform that enables distributed teams to work effectively together, from brainstorming with digital sticky notes to planning and managing agile workflows.

Without being constrained by physical location, meeting space or whiteboards, Miro enables remote, in-office and hybrid teams to interact across formats, tools, channels and timezones. The whiteboard platform Miro is excellent for group learning. This open-source tool definitely works for organizing concepts while promoting teamwork. Teams can discuss, organize activities, provide/request feedback and comments, present various thoughts, etc. because of its simple and clear design. The portal also includes sections for discussion, comments, and videos. Additionally, inviting others to work together is simple. Miro offers free and paid plans.

With Miro, you can arrange meetings and workshops, take use of a comprehensive range of collaboration options and make cross-functional teamwork simple by utilizing features like video chat, presentations, sharing and many more.

5.4 Area 4 - Assessment

PlayPosit

[Playposit](#) is an interactive web-based video platform that allows educators to provide formative assessments both inside and outside the classroom. Trainers are able to embed quiz-type questions into videos from Youtube, Vimeo, Khan Academy, and other popular video platforms. Data can then be analyzed on the individual or group level, providing powerful insight into educational trends in the classroom.

Instructors may create and edit interactive video assessments using the PlayPosit application for the web and Google Chrome. In order to make an interactive movie or bulb, trainers upload an audio file or a video from well-known websites like (e.g. YouTube). Three options are available on the straightforward interface: video segments, interactions, and reviews. Users may mix and trim videos using those tabs. They can also add closed captions and features like polls, multiple-choice questions, conversation breaks, and written comments with optional feedback. Trainers short on time may also do a filtered search through tens of thousands of readymade bulbs, copy them to their dashboard, and make any necessary edits. Videos can be modified by trainers to include helpful affordances for learners, such as the ability to rewind, fast-forward, skip interactions, or redo the session. Also, trainers may monitor progress on the dashboard after learners begin receiving their allocated bulbs and begin to complete them.

Unlimited bulbs are available in the free version, however, there are only 100 tries each month for learners. Each instructor receives a total of 100 learner attempts every calendar month. Therefore, if you have a single class with 25 learners, you may provide that class with four bulbs each month. This limitation is removed in the premium version.

Socrative

[Socrative](#) is a platform where trainers can use online quizzes and real-time assessments to assess learners. With Socrative, you can make your own tests, have them evaluated automatically and generate reports to see how everyone performed.

There is no need to install any hardware because Socrative is a web-based platform that works with Mac, Windows and Chrome-based operating systems. All you need is an internet-connected desktop, laptop or mobile device and a web browser that supports HTML-5. There are two versions of Socrative: free and paid. With the free one, trainers can have up to 50 learners in a room taking a quiz and a single room. For as long as you require, the activity can be conducted in a room. Once you click the Finish button in the Results area of your account, the activity will be locked to learners. Create whatever kind of activity best matches your needs, from tests to surveys. You may mix up the questions, make your activity anonymous, or give immediate feedback. Multiple choice, true/false, and short answer questions are all acceptable and the order of the questions can be randomly assigned to each learner.

An essential component of the learning process is immediate feedback. With Socrative, you can efficiently monitor and assess learner learning in the classroom or at work, saving time for trainers and fostering enjoyable and engaging interactions for learners.

CrowdSignal

[CrowdSignal](#) is an online website where you can make polls, surveys, quizzes and ratings, as well as share and analyse the results. CrowdSignal is a user-friendly evaluation tool that will improve the way you teach.

Creating an account is necessary, and you may select from a variety of pricing plans. The free plan does not cost money and it still allows you to generate polls, quizzes, surveys and reports. It's really easy to set up and utilize CrowdSignal. Simply select the assessment type you wish to construct, drag and drop the different question types into the desired sequence and then put in the necessary prompts and response options. Customize the appearance by choosing a colour that complements your assessment. Choose from one of the pre-made themes or create your own. The survey is then available for sharing through a link, email or posting to a separate website. Obtaining reports for any of these evaluations is likewise fairly simple. They can be exported to apps like Google Sheets and Excel and analyzed.

This website is excellent for producing brief tests that may be utilized at the start, middle, or finish of a course or class. There are many different question types in the tests, polls, and surveys, and you can quickly and simply view the results to enhance your training. To encourage your trainees to become more reflective learners, you may even share the findings.

Formative

[Formative](#) is an interactive learner response and evaluation tool that is web and app-based and works with practically any device. The trainers create the assignment, while the trainees complete the tasks and submit them for feedback.

Here are some things you can do on Formative. You can create formative assessments from scratch or grab templates from the library. There is a free wide range of question types, such as free responses, multiple choice, multiple selections, short answer, show your work, audio response, categorize questions, drag and drop, file response, fill in the blank and many more. Once this is settled, assign formatives to learners. Watch them respond live, give instant feedback and leverage auto-grading. Track learners and class growth over time and performance in specific standards. You can see which learners have not started the formative, have started but not submitted, and which have submitted. You can also collaborate with teams of trainers from your organization.

With the help of Formative, quickly create basic or in-depth evaluations, monitoring your learners and giving them feedback in real-time. Trainers may develop new superpowers, increase learner engagement, and accelerate learning with the use of Formative.

Poll Everywhere

[Poll Everywhere](#) is a learner-response tool that offers whole-class participation and assessment through trainer-designed surveys, polls and discussion boards.

Although the design is a little outdated, trainers may keep it interesting by mixing up the response options, and learners can respond to their classmates' real-time responses. Polls may be quickly created by trainers and used as a single question or a series of questions. Every poll has the ability to accept responses from a variety of devices, so learners can use a smartphone, portable device, tablet, laptop, or computer to text or cast an online ballot. When the poll is presented, learners can respond

by following the instructions there. They reply by texting the number displayed on the screen, or trainers can obtain a unique URL to distribute to learners so they can reply on the web app or even on Twitter. For each poll, trainers may specify the choices for how they wish to accept replies.

Using Poll Everywhere as a formative assessment technique may improve and amplify the class conversation, participation, and comprehension. Trainers may prefer to withhold results until all learners have responded and this is possible.

Mentimeter

[Mentimeter](#) is an interactive presentation tool that allows users to engage their audiences in real-time. It assists in resolving the issue of repeatedly selecting the same learners by soliciting input from the whole class.

This interactive presentation tool enables users to connect with their audiences in real-time. Trainers can register by using their email addresses, Google, Facebook logins or both. Users have a selection of Events to pick from, including options like queries, polls, word clouds, comments, and more. To access the questions and to join, users must input a six-digit join code from the app or menti.com. While Events are restricted to two per presentation, Trainers are allowed to create up to five quizzes for free. Since the free edition lacks exporting options, trainers can only view data.

Engage with learners with live polls, word clouds, quizzes, multiple-choice questions and more with Mentimeter. Ask questions, analyze the answers and keep track of your learners' comprehension and learning. Interact and communicate with them.

5.5 Area 5 - Empowering learners

Learner Variability Navigator

[Learner variability navigator](#) is a free online tool that converts the science of learner variability into understandable learner factor maps and approaches to enhance the design of educational products and classroom instruction.

The trainers have to choose a model that represents their area of interest. It can be Math, Literacy or general adult learner. Being able to effectively employ reading, numeracy, problem-solving, communication and digital abilities in a variety of situations is one of the objectives of adult learning. The trainers may create tools and classes that support all learners by having a thorough understanding of the learner factors, techniques and connections that have an influence. Learner Variability Navigator gives information about factors and strategies for developing learner background (adverse experiences, physical well-being, socioeconomic status etc.), social and emotional learning (emotion, learner mindset, motivation etc.), cognition (attention, metacognition, short-term memory etc.) and literacies (composition, digital literacy, oral communication skills etc.).

Research in the learning sciences sheds light on the most effective ways to engage and support the entire variety of learners. Therefore, LVN transforms this constantly expanding research into understandable variables and approaches that can influence both product design and classroom instruction. These models utilize a whole-person framework and are free.

ClassroomScreen

With [ClassroomScreen](#) trainers have a lot of possibilities to support their class activities, stimulate engagement and help their learners get to work. ClassroomScreen is an online tool that includes 19 widgets to create clear expectations for the learners, support time management, collect feedback and much more.

The features include: setting a background, poll, random name, QR code generator, drawing tool, sound level, work symbols, timer, clock, stopwatch, calendar, dice, embed links, group maker, and adding images or text. For example, the work symbol feature lets learners know under what conditions they can work on their task. Choose from: 'work together', 'ask neighbour', 'whisper' or 'silence'. Another great feature is the sound level. The trainer needs to connect a microphone and measure the sound level in their class. If learners make too much noise, a bell will ring to indicate they have to be quieter.

ClassroomScreen is free, simple, useful, accessible and intuitive. No matter the subject area, ClassroomScreen can be used anytime as long as the classroom has a projector, interactive whiteboard or television.

Kahoot!

[Kahoot!](#) is a game-based learning platform that makes it simple to quickly develop, share and play learning games or trivia quizzes in minutes. The trainer creates (or chooses from existing) games and trainees play together on their own devices.

A gamification tool called Kahoot! enables corporate trainers and educators to produce interactive presentations, training materials and educational games. To ensure maximum engagement, people may study for exams utilizing flashcards, games, quizzes, and peer challenges. It's preferable to play Kahoots as a group. You need a special PIN in order to join a game. You require a large screen if you are the game's host. Questions are shown on a shared screen, and players respond on their own devices. In addition to sending players live games, you can also send Kahoot tasks for homework or remote training that they may do on their own time. Kahoot! gives corporate trainers the ability to include quiz questions with slides, open-ended questions, polls, word clouds and more; stream live presentations on learners' devices; share training materials with workers. Goal-setting, performance measurements, activity monitoring, and rewards administration are some of Kahoot! key features.

In addition, the tool allows educators to do formative evaluations because it is easy for educators to measure how well their classes are learning by seeing game reports.

Jeopardy!

[Jeopardy](#) is a wonderful game to play when you need to review a significant amount of material and want your learners to stay involved.

Anyone who has played Jeopardy before would recognize the quiz format, which makes it accessible to both trainers and trainees. The architecture is built on points, and questions may be quickly accessed and responded to with a few clicks, enabling use across different devices. Once the questions are settled, the only thing left to do is choose how many teams will participate, and the game may begin immediately. Every time a team selects a topic area, they must also select a question from that

category that relates to a given cash amount (\$100, \$200, \$300, etc.). Give teams a minute to appropriately respond to each chosen question. Before presenting the solution, team members must work together. Whether the response is right or wrong, then it is the turn of the following team. Each team has more opportunities to participate during the game when they take turns.

Any of these rules can be adapted to meet the needs of the learners and to meet your own preferences for running games in your classroom. Also, these quizzes may be printed, which is a great helpful feature if you want to offer any to the class or one to be taken home to do later.

Assistive technology

Assistive technology (AT) is the use of devices and software to improve the experience of learning or going about daily life. AT can range from Braille displays and books to text-to-speech software or wheelchairs.

Some examples of assistive technology are:

- [Speechify](#) – converts text into audio by turning it into voice;
- [Tactplus](#) – a Braille printer;
- [Co:Writer](#) – transcribe speech and predict intended words and phrases;
- [Dragon](#) – speech recognition software;
- [Quillsoft](#) – assists in writing and reading;
- [Jaws](#) – screen reader;
- [Microsoft](#) – on-screen keyboard, speech recognition, magnifier etc.
- [Adobe Reader](#) – convert text to speech.

Assistive technology needs to be used in conjunction with high-quality training in order to be successful. Also, for the implementation of assistive technology, trainers need training.

5.6 Area 6 - Facilitating learners' digital competences

Media and information literacy curriculum for trainers

[Media and information literacy curriculum](#) for trainers is Published by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) in 2011. Its goal is to offer teachers educational programs in developed and developing nations a framework for creating a curriculum that produces educators who are media and information literate.

There are two sections to this book. The MIL Curriculum and Competency Framework, which is presented in the first part, provides a summary of the rationale, design, and major concepts of the curriculum. It complements the UNESCO Framework for Teachers' ICT Competencies (2008). The curriculum's comprehensive Core and Non-Core Modules are included in the second part.

The textbook includes the following chapters: Introduction, Unifying notions of media and information literacy, Benefits and requirements of MIL, Main topics of the MIL curriculum for teachers, The Curriculum framework, Policy and vision, Knowledge of media and information for democratic discourse and social participation, Evaluation of media and information, Media and information

production and use, Core teacher competencies and Pedagogies in the teaching and learning of MIL using the curriculum.

Google Scholar

[Google Scholar](#) is a search engine that enables users to look for academic materials and scholarly literature from a variety of fields. Search across a variety of subjects and sources from one location, including academic publishers, professional associations, online repositories, institutions, and other websites. This includes articles, theses, books, abstracts, and court judgments. Google Scholar assists you in locating pertinent research within the intellectual community.

Searching is as simple as using the standard Google interface. Like regular Google, Google Scholar returns the most relevant results first. They are arranged in relevant order based on full-text matching, publication location, author identity, and the number of citations. There is also an advanced search with more options. You might, however, occasionally desire greater control over what your search accomplishes. The Advanced Scholar Search menu might be useful when you need to accomplish this. It is possible to modify the publication date, look for results from a certain author or journal, provide synonyms, or exclude undesirable results.

The usage of Google Scholar search should be intuitive if you currently utilize the Google search engine. So, switching to Google Scholar should be simple and comfortable. Moreover, the fact that this academic search engine is free is an additional benefit.

WorldWideScience

[WorldWideScience](#) is a federation of national scientific websites where research output is made public by member countries, offering comprehensive coverage of international science and research output beyond linguistic boundaries.

Currently, WorldWideScience allows users to search through around 100 databases and portals from more than 70 nations. org. Users have access to the most recent research in a variety of sectors, including fundamental sciences, energy, medicine, agriculture, and the environment. A large portion of the material retrieved through this gateway is public domain and publicly accessible. One of the many benefits provided by WorldWideScience.org's federated search engine is the user's ability to conduct a real-time, simultaneous search across several databases. A user is given a compiled list of results that are sorted by relevance and include data in text, multimedia, and scientific formats.

Moreover, multilingual translations are automatically performed in ten languages, which makes scholarly material more accessible to a worldwide audience. Data sets may be searched using WorldWideScience.org in a way that makes it easier for people to find research data.

ResearchGate

[ResearchGate](#) is a well-known online social networking and academic profile site for exchanging academic articles. It is a source of free scientific papers because many scientists and researchers submit PDF versions of their works there. They're often included in Google Scholar.

Connect with colleagues, co-authors, and specialists in your field, ask research-related questions and get answers from experts and share your knowledge and expertise. Learners can, however, also utilize this website to access the resources offered. People will be able to ask for the texts. On one hand, it is

needed to wait a few days for the approval of some texts from the researchers. On the other hand, some texts are completely free and available. Furthermore, in order to log in, you need your institutional email address. If you want to seek an account and you have an institutional email address that the website doesn't recognize or maybe you don't have an institutional one, then the request will be manually handled.

That being said, ResearchGate allows you to make research visible and assists you in finding material useful to your job. It is an academic social networking site used to collaborate and ask questions and find reliable papers.

Semantic Scholar

[Semantic Scholar](#) provides free, AI-driven search and discovery tools, and open resources for the global research community. It indexes more than 200 million scholarly works that come through collaborations with publishers, data suppliers, and web crawls.

To improve the reading experience, Semantic Reader employs artificial intelligence to comprehend a document's structure and combine it with the academic corpus of Semantic Scholar, providing detailed information in context via tooltips and other overlays. When you log in to Semantic Scholar, you may save and arrange all the articles that interest you in your online library and access them from anywhere at any time. You may group papers into specific folders in your library and export citations in bulk. You may also establish AI-powered Research Feeds that will automatically provide paper suggestions for you after creating a folder. Toggle each folder's Research Feed to "On," and you'll start getting recommendations on a regular basis starting the next day.

Those who are interested in a particular subject may quickly grasp a publication using Semantic Scholar. Its approach analyzes articles to uncover connections and significance, then reveals these discoveries to assist Scholars in finding and comprehending research.

Conclusions and recommendations

The Digital Facilitator Toolkit is a document for adults 55+ learners' educators and adult education centres staff that are living in the digital transition and detected the need for an up-to-date teaching/learning experience.

To advance the lifelong learning and integration of adults 55+ in society and to ease their transition from employment to retirement, the entire educational construct needs to be adapted compared to other age groups. This educational construct includes, for example, answering fundamental questions such as: what topics are being addressed, where the training activities take place, when or for what period and, most importantly, how the training and non-formal education is being designed and delivered. The answer to these questions rests with the adult education providers but, ultimately, with their trainers and facilitators who work directly with adults 55+.

The Covid-19 pandemic restricted to a great extent many facilitators and trainers from organising face-to-face activities. This required trainers to learn how to design and deliver activities using digital tools but also to train adults 55+ on using those digital tools. Overall, the profile of trainers changed from facilitators to digital facilitators. Therefore, a change in the vision towards digitalization has to be promoted among adult 55+ learners: being online and digitally present is not only about social networking or messaging. This transition has to be always more clear in the teaching/learning service, with guided consecutive levels of competence and acquirable subsequent degrees of expertise.

The research survey carried out showed the need for trustable and qualified personnel in adult education centres, especially when adults, with different study and work backgrounds, have to learn about a very conflictual topic.

As the desk research showed, there are valuable examples of good practices in the project partner countries and across Europe. It follows that advancing the digital transformation of facilitators and adults 55+ could take advantage of these good practices, provided that these practices are promoted to reach decision-makers and influencers in adult education centres.

The competence map, as well as the self-assessment questionnaire, are in line with EU DigComp and DigCompEdu frameworks, promoting the empowerment and engagement of citizens towards ICT in all aspects of their lives. Moreover, they are objectified to the specific group of digital facilitators of adults 55+. Using the map and the self-assessment tool together for the professional development of digital facilitators would improve awareness of the competences required and the default (current) competence levels of those facilitators.

Moreover, the manual expanded the research into the tools that may assist digital facilitators of adults 55+ in rounding their knowledge, attitudes and skills in the six areas that compose the competence map. These will further assist field educators in designing and delivering digital courses, including face-to-face, hybrid and online courses that employ digital technology to support the creation and delivery of non formal courses for adults 55+.

The toolbox assembled by the research team and included in this manual is structured to mirror the competence map. However, readers may note that many of these tools address more than one competence area. At the same time, the toolbox is far from being exhaustive but represents a good starting point for all adult educators in their attempt to improve their competences as digital facilitators for adults 55+.

Usability and transferability

This manual is part of the Erasmus+ project “[DIFA - Digital Facilitator for Adults 55+](#)”, implemented by a consortium of four partners from Romania, Spain and Turkey. The DIFA55+ project aims to develop, test and implement an innovative digital education ecosystem with supportive tools to let educators create, share and adapt attractive learning activities for the development of digital skills of adults 55+.

As shown by our research, educators need specific training to be able to guide and advise learners in their turn. To support this, in this manual the project researchers and adult educators developed a research methodology, implemented it through primary research (survey) and desk research (finding and analysing good practices), fed the research into a competence map, developed an online self-assessment tool for digital facilitators of adults 55+ and curated a toolbox which assists digital facilitators of adults 55+ in bridging their competence gaps.

The manual addresses primarily digital facilitators of adults 55+. However, indirect beneficiaries are also adults 55+, who may take advantage of the good practices and tools provided. Family members of adults 55+ may also find inspiration from this manual on how to best assist their loved ones. Beneficiaries of this manual are also organizations and institutions such as adult education centres, social assistance offices, retirement houses and adult education centres.

In addition, the manual may add the greatest value to disadvantaged learners and people with fewer opportunities, including people with disabilities and those facing economic difficulties. All these people can access the current manual and the associated online support platforms and tools.

While the generic category of users includes primarily digital facilitators of adults 55+, the manual may also be utilized in other areas including school, higher education, vocational and youth education (for intergenerational activities, for example). Therefore, the category of potential users of this manual extends to teachers, researchers, university professors, social workers and youth workers.

In the following paragraphs, we outline the elements that can be used by the direct target groups or transferred to other target groups. We define usability as the ways in which the content can be used to achieve the required goals effectively and efficiently (Jordan, 2002). In comparison, transferability is the degree to which the content is relevant and applicable to other similar situations (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

The specific procedures or techniques used to identify, select, process, and analyse information about this specific topic can be transferred to any qualitative research. The methodology used for primary and secondary research flows in a way suitable for any other research, no matter its topic.

Firstly, the structure of the manual may be transferred to many other topics. It includes a summary, content, introduction to the subject matter, methodology, research results, good practices, competence map, self-assessment instrument, tools for digital facilitators of adults 55+, conclusions and recommendations, information about the authors and partner organisations and references.

The research methodology developed and implemented by the research consortium in line with the DIFA55+ project objectives, qualitative and quantitative performance indicators is transferable to any other similar research.

The primary research survey methodology including data collection and analysis of results is also transferable to other research endeavours. Moreover, the research results regarding adult learners' readiness for digital media in their surroundings may be used in other projects as a starting point, justification or development of educational materials.

The good practices identified and collected in **Chapter 3** may be used by digital facilitators and their organisations to support their educational services for adults 55+ and adults in general. These may be further explained to foster awareness or adapted and implemented in public institutions and private organisations working with adults 55+.

The competence map and the [online self-assessment instrument](#) designed by the research team to identify competence gaps in the six areas set out by the DigCompEdu framework may be used per se, adapted to particular narrower categories of target groups or utilised as good practice examples of competence maps and online assessment tools for other topics and target groups.

The collection of tools which assist digital facilitators of adults 55+ in bridging the competence gaps may be used to assist digital facilitators of other target groups in rounding their knowledge, attitudes and skills in the six areas that compose the competence map. These may further assist field educators in designing and delivering digital courses (face-to-face, hybrid or online courses that employ digital technology).

Finally, the conclusions and recommendations formulated in this manual may be used for other target groups and educational contexts.

All the items mentioned above are included in this written manual for digital facilitators of adults 55+. However, this manual should be regarded as a complementary component of the entire educational package being developed and provided in the DIFA55+ project.

The methodology of the needs analysis research is primarily based on desk research and a survey questionnaire. The specific procedures or techniques used to identify, select, process and analyse information about this specific topic can be transferred to any other field. The methodology used for primary and secondary research flows in a way suitable for research on other topics as well. The results themselves can be used not only by adult educators and digital facilitators but also by other people dealing with adults 55+, including families and social workers.

Perhaps the ultimate evidence of the usability and transferability of the DIFA55+ educational ecosystem is that the self-assessment tool can be provided upon request to other institutions and could easily be installed in any Moodle platform (Moodle accounts for over 200 million users and 151,000 websites). In addition, this is compatible with most online learning systems available in the market (Moodle or not).

Currently, all the project deliverables and activities are freely available in various formats on the DIFA55+ project webpage and the TrainingClub.eu Moodle platform (which is available in its web and mobile app versions). Upon the completion of the DIFA55+ project, the materials and their online references will be made available through the Erasmus+ Project Results Platform (EPRP).

But even if the materials are made available online, users' learning can take place virtually anywhere: at home in front of a computer, tablet or smartphone; at the premises of partner organisations, in adult education and training centres, in senior care centres, etc. and at work.

Another benefit of the DIFA55+ education ecosystem is that the online is an environment that never sleeps, the MOOC is always open (unlike other courses where registration takes place from time to time), the educational resources are always available online and anyone can learn anytime (not necessarily in the same place or at the same time). All these are made available to any teacher, trainer and digital facilitator to organise classes 24/7 around the year, every year, no matter of time zone. Everything will be maintained and updated for many years from now.

So far, we presented a comprehensive image of why we developed these educational materials, for whom, what is included in the educational package, where is this available and when could be accessed. In the following, we focus on how can these educational materials be utilised by users and transferred to target groups.

From the learners' perspective, these materials are suitable for both training and self-study activities. They can be used online as MOOC, in synchronous and asynchronous modes, in closed groups or for face-to-face classes.

From the digital trainers' perspective, this educational package could be used online, hybrid or face-to-face. For example, some may wish to study the materials by themselves online and then download them to deliver face-to-face in class. However, to ensure that the participants followed the learning steps, educators could ask learners to follow the online self-assessment and present the results of the self-assessment test including the radar plot.

It should also be noted that the resources are available online for people with disabilities. In our Moodle, we implemented an accessibility pack for those with visual impairments. The self-assessment is compatible with machine reading software which makes it available for learners and educators with special needs.

Last, but not least, our consortium adheres to a set of guiding principles in terms of transparency, integration and copyright.

Transparency is a principle that attracts possible partners and any person who is interested in this topic or a specific organization. The current manual that has been created can be found online and accessed by anyone. Furthermore, anybody can enrol on the MOOC platform and access the self-assessment tool.

The project methodologies, resources, processes, results and outcomes were incorporated into partner organizations. This is the focal point of our approach since it enhances partners' capabilities (competences and resources) and demonstrates that our educational and managerial approach works. In the end, the goal is to make sure that other organizations adapt and use successfully the tools, techniques or lessons that we developed.

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About partner organisations

TEAM4Excellence (T4E) is a Romanian association aiming to improve the quality of life through education, research and consulting activities. To address societal challenges, T4E provides learning opportunities and career advice for social inclusion, development and employability of people, and equips trainers with key competences and skills to foster personal as well as professional development. Within 30+ EU-funded projects, the association produces and transfers innovation, experience and know-how through cooperation with domestic and international partners. By hosting events,

training courses and conferences, T4E strengthens collaboration between people, supports organisations and bridges gaps between generations. The wide expertise in management enables T4E staff to provide consultancy to large companies and SMEs using EFQM Model and Business Model Canvas.

Sarıçam Halk Eğitimi Merkezi (Sarıçam Public Education Center) is a public institution founded in 2009 in Adana, Türkiye and affiliated with the Ministry of National Education's Directorate General for Lifelong Learning. Sarıçam HEM, which provides training services all year, including weekends and evenings, performs tasks in accordance with the principles and objectives of non-formal education. Since 2010, Sarıçam HEM has been in charge of the execution and planning of adult education services in the areas

of education, training, guidance, information access, counselling, culture, arts, and sports. Sarıçam HEM provides non-formal educational activities in collaboration with various governmental and private institutions, as well as volunteer organisations. Its main responsibilities include implementing training activities, as well as assisting and monitoring training activities. Sarıçam HEM also conducts activities aimed at ensuring the adaptation of adults who have not completed formal education to the constantly changing technological, social, and cultural conditions.

Formative Footprint (FFSL) is an educational design organization located in Spain, in the province of Valladolid. FFSL is specialized in the design and creation of new training processes tailored to the specific needs of the 21st century. Based on personal and professional needs, FFSL implements a methodical process that ensures the creation of new practical and successful educational processes that manage to stop previously detected needs/problems that organizations and citizens have. Formative Footprint has built up a team of

professional experts in education, training and innovation. This brought the organization to work as a training and research centre, specialised in topics related on one hand to education and training, on the other hand to innovation.

Asociația Voluntariat Pentru Viață is an NGO, based in Marasesti, Romania, founded in 2012 on the initiative of some specialists in the field of education, art, history and social assistance. Their mission is to promote volunteering and civic consciousness by developing activities that respond to the local need of the community to become aware of the value of volunteering as a tool for active citizenship and human solidarity. A large part of the activities is focused on supporting disadvantaged people to have access to education. The association is accredited as a social services provider and it

implements projects involving elderly care services at home and in residential centres. To offer multidisciplinary services for individuals who are in a critical social difficulty, they conduct social research and monitor the phenomenon of social exclusion, plan programs of assistance for individuals who are in social crisis and train professionals in working with underprivileged people.

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Appendix. Template to collect good practices

<i>Name</i>	
<i>Description</i>	
<i>Key Stakeholders/Provider</i>	
<i>Level</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Organizational <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> International
<i>Topic (problem solved, issue addressed)</i>	
<i>Skills acquired or enhanced</i>	
<i>Impact/Success factors (with statics, if available)</i>	
<i>Tools/Resources/Services</i>	
<i>Link/ Website</i>	

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